

RISK, CARE AND INNOVATION:
TWENTY YEARS OF THE
feminist review | **TRUST**

Carrie Hamilton

feminist review | **TRUST**

We would like to thank the many readers who reviewed our short-listed selections in the early years of the Trust.

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PREFACE

The Feminist Review Trust was established over 20 years ago as a unique project: a feminist academic journal using its profits to support activist projects across the world. In that time we have funded over 180 projects and distributed over half a million pounds.

The Trust is now closing. The exigences of academic precarity and the demands placed on academics today are very different to those in place when the Trust was founded.

We do not want the Trust, its uniqueness and its contribution to the support of activist feminists to be lost. So, as part of our closure, we have commissioned two reports: one on our history and another an evaluation of our work, in the hope that others might find our experiences informative.

And, as our last political act as socialist feminists and as Trustees, we will be donating the residue of our funds to Medical Aid to Palestine to support women and children.

The Trustees of the Feminist Review Trust.
August 2024.

RISK, CARE AND INNOVATION: TWENTY YEARS OF THE FEMINIST REVIEW TRUST

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

In 2022, I was commissioned to write a history of the Feminist Review Trust (FRT). The FRT was founded in 2001 and became a feminist charitable foundation in 2005. After twenty years of funding feminist projects around the world, in 2021 the Trust began the process of closing down.

I want to extend my thanks to all current Trustees for sharing their memories with generosity and frankness, including highlighting favourite projects, being candid about the Trust's challenges as well as its successes, and sending documents relating to many of the awards, including those highlighted below.

I'm also grateful to Eleanor O'Gorman for sharing with me her Learning Review of the Trust, "Funding Feminist Change – 20 Years of Action & Solidarity by the Feminist Review Trust".

I was a Feminist Review Trustee between 2014 and 2018, and a member of the Feminist Review Collective from 2012 to 2019. These experiences have shaped my understanding of the Trust's history. However, the highlights, challenges and conclusions outlined below have been drawn first and foremost from the Trust's archives, including reports and documents pertaining to projects funded by the Trust, as well as extensive interviews with the current Board of Trustees. Quotations from case studies are taken from applications and other relevant documents in the possession of the Feminist Review Trust.

INTRODUCTION

The story of the Trust was a story about how a group of feminists who had some money decided to give out tiny bits of money to different groups that made a huge difference. FR Trustee

The whole project was an ongoing risk. FR Trustee

Breastfeeding, Crisis and Equalities (2016)

In 2016, the Feminist Review Trust funded the project **Breastfeeding, Crisis and Inequalities**. Initiated by Mammias, a community organisation founded in 2009 and run by and for women in the Spinney Hill and Highfields areas of Leicester, the project aimed “to address and support the rights of mothers facing hardship and crisis to breastfeed their babies.” The neighbourhoods covered by Mammias are among the poorest in the UK, with high levels of health, economic and gender inequality, and where 47% of children live in poverty.

The organisation’s aim is to reduce social and economic inequalities by offering all women, regardless of income or situation, the opportunity to breastfeed and provide the best possible start in life to their children. Its members represent seven faith communities and a number of ethnic groups, speak over twenty-five languages and come from more than twenty countries. They have different levels of education, both large and smaller families, young as well as older children (and parents!), single mothers, mothers and children with disabilities, LGBTQ+ women, asylum seekers, women working in different professions and grandmothers.

In the words of the organisation’s mission statement:

Mammias aims to promote the health and well-being of mothers and babies, through the support, protection and promotion of breastfeeding, and through creating a better understanding of mother–baby relationships.

Mammias operates in the context of ongoing national and international debates over breastfeeding. Although the communities it serves generally view breastfeeding as natural, “there are nevertheless a number of myths and misunderstandings which can prevent mothers getting the support they may need”. Yet few charities and community organisations in the UK are dedicated to supporting pregnant women and new mothers. Moreover, language differences, isolation and a lack of information on the availability of free services for these women can act as barriers to accessing services.

In January 2016, the first All-Party Parliamentary Group (APPG) for Infant Feeding and Inequalities was founded. Mammias noted that most members of the APPG represented communities where the majority of breastfeeding women were white British. Wishing to ensure that that Black and Minority Ethnic (BME) new mothers were represented, the group sought Trust funding to send two people to APPG meetings. In addition to representing a largely unrepresented community, Mammias members' attendance at these meetings would allow breastfeeding peer supporters from BME communities in Leicester "to access skills and learning at the level needed to enhance their understanding and knowledge of breastfeeding", and to participate fully in the political arena at national level.

According to Mammias' funding application:

The aim of the project funded by the Feminist Review Trust grant is to increase political understanding and involvement in both UK mainstream politics, and in the politics of motherhood, babies and breastfeeding, locally, nationally and globally. We also wanted to strengthen our voice within the national breastfeeding arena. Most of those attending national conferences and committees are White British, despite the fact that women from BME backgrounds are more likely to breastfeed than their White British counterparts.

Funding was also sought for five Mammias volunteers to attend the UNICEF Baby Friendly Conference, the largest infant feeding conference in Europe, and to hold five workshops in their communities in Leicester.

As the recipients of the award noted in their report to the Trust:

In July 2017 we were awarded a contract by Leicestershire Partnership NHS Trust to deliver breastfeeding peer support services for the city, focusing on wards with high levels of deprivation and inequalities. This was in great part because of our track record in ensuring all our users have a strong voice, and in our ability to use innovative and creative ways to reach beyond the confines that many far better resourced programmes are able to. The award from the Feminist Review Trust played a great part in this. It has brought us confidence and increased our belief in ourselves, as well as opened the eyes of our volunteers to the role of politics in all its guises in every aspect of life, but especially in the roles of mothers and women. The women in our organisation face many barriers to inclusion in much of mainstream British politics and life. This has meant that it has not always been easy for them to take advantage of the opportunities even with the funding available, due to family or work pressures. However, they are always interested to know more about the events attended by Mammias representatives, and it generates plenty of discussion on our WhatsApp groups. The award has also enabled us to raise our profile across the UK world of breastfeeding. We are frequently approached by researchers into pregnancy and new motherhood looking for women from less advantaged and more diverse communities than they may be able to access within their usual contacts. For an organisation of our size that is a great achievement,

and really helps us serve our community, and the wider community of less privileged women and especially mothers of young children.

One Mamma who attended the conference reported:

It was something I needed, and something I could do for myself, because when you have kids, life sort of revolves round them, and you don't really think about yourself. This sort of put the two together in a way that to be honest I didn't think was possible.

Trust funding not only paid for the work Mammias had originally applied for, but also made the organisation more attractive to other funders and boosted their confidence, to the extent that some Mammias members subsequently travelled to London to lobby Parliament.

In the words of one FR Trustee:

Mammias is a wonderful example of where our grant leveraged a huge amount – in money, scope of work and presence.

This brief history of the Feminist Review Trust (FRT) opens with the story of one of the innovative and impactful projects funded by the Trust during the first two decades of the twenty-first century. The Mammias initiative exemplifies how small amounts of direct, focused feminist funding were able to support an organisation to achieve concrete goals and develop greater resources in an area of substantial and previously unmet need.

Founded in 2001 by members of the editorial board of the academic journal *Feminist Review*, the FRT was an independent feminist funder based in London. Over a period of twenty years, it gave money to some 188 feminist projects (see p.15), distributing over half a million pounds throughout the UK and around the world.

This is the story of how a small feminist funder made some big differences during a period of ongoing economic crisis and austerity, as well as significant challenges to, and changes in, feminist organising worldwide.

BEGINNINGS

Exacerbated by war and ethnic conflict, women around the globe are battling with the consequences of gender inequality: huge disparities in the distribution of wealth, racism, violence and engrained patriarchal attitudes denying women education as well as social and sexual rights. Many projects and local initiatives designed to support and empower women, however, struggle to find funds to achieve their aims.

The Feminist Review Trust was established in 2001 to help such projects. The Trust came out of, and is funded by, Feminist Review, the founding, flagship, UK feminist collective journal. The Trust is a unique charity. It prioritizes giving to women's projects – in the poorest countries as well as from the UK. Every year the Trust contributes to a wide range of groups and organizations that make a real difference to women's lives.

Feminist Trust Appeal, 2014

The very fact of someone coming up with the idea of using the money from an academic journal to fund feminist work is very important.

FR Trustee

The history of the FRT stands at the crossroads of several key questions for feminism in the late twentieth and early twenty-first centuries:

- What is feminism?
- How is money a feminist issue?
- What kind of feminist activism is most likely to effect the greatest change – not only in women's daily lives, but in the very structures of gender relations?
- How do feminists reconcile the demands of activism with the challenges presented by the increased marketisation of higher education and other sectors, job insecurity and widespread economic precarity?
- How do we measure the impact of feminist work and funding on women's lives, and on societies more broadly?

The Trust was a product of a very particular moment in feminist history in the United Kingdom and globally. It was founded by editors of *Feminist Review (FR)*, a British-based socialist and feminist academic journal established in 1979. From the start, *FR* stood out among academic journals for being run not by a hierarchical board of editors but by a

Collective. The Trust's beginnings therefore sat within a long tradition of feminist commitment to practice-led theory, and the Trust continued the activist work of the journal.

The FRT emerged at a time of significant change for feminist academia, part of what has more generally been characterised as the neoliberalisation of universities in the UK and elsewhere.¹ In the words of one Trustee:

These years were the beginning of the end of a certain version of education. There was a lot of firefighting going on. Neoliberalism was getting more and more celebratory.

By the end of the twentieth century, Women's and Gender Studies departments and courses, many established in UK universities during the heady years of the feminist second wave in the 1970s, were increasingly under threat. The same Trustee recalls that just as the FRT was being set up, managers at her university were trying to shut down the Women's Studies programme in which she worked.

In the same period around the turn of the millennium, more and more feminist and left-leaning scholarly journals were moving to big commercial publishers. *Feminist Review* went against the grain of this trend. The journal became a limited company early on and the *FR* Collective retained ownership of the company. For this reason, Collective members were able to take the lead in choosing a publisher that would respect the journal's grounding in feminist activism. In the late 1990s, *FR* was approached by David Bell from the publisher Macmillan. When the publisher asked Bell to bring in a successful social science journal to add to Macmillan's collection, he chose *FR*. Bell was impressed by and committed to the journal's political and intellectual vision, and was also drawn to its substantial university library subscription base. With Bell's support, the *FR* Collective was able to secure a unique profit-sharing arrangement with Macmillan. Thanks to this, the journal turned a small but significant annual profit from its subscriptions. This put the *FR* Collective in the unusual situation of being an activist feminist collective with surplus funds to spend. Collective members decided to establish a trust in order to redistribute its profits to small women's and feminist projects within and outside academia, thereby honouring the journal's founding commitment to feminist praxis.

¹ See, for example, Alpesh Maisuria and Mike Cole, "The neoliberalization of higher education in England: An alternative is possible", *Policy Futures in Education* 15, 5 (2017): 602–19.

The idea to give the money made by an academic journal to grassroots feminist projects nationally and around the world made the *Feminist Review* project unique. One of the new generation of Trustees, who joined the Trust in its final years, recalled being attracted to this radical model:

I'd done my Masters, and I was vaguely aware that there's this journal publishing industry making lots of money on the backs of free labour, so I thought, "Well, if there is money coming into the system, let's get it out again."

The years when the Trust was established were also ones in which members of the *FR* collective were examining their own roles in political struggles inside and outside the journal. In particular, what former *FR* Collective member Gail Lewis has called the *interventions* of Black and other women of colour – including ongoing interventions to call white feminists to account for racism within the Collective and in the wider feminist movement – were (as they continue to be) fundamental in shaping the politics of the journal, as well as its intellectual priorities and working practices.²

One of the Trust's founding members recalls how those interventions helped to define the priorities of the Trust. As more women of colour joined the *Feminist Review* Collective, discussions about racism pushed the journal towards centring race, ethnicity and migration in its pages. In her words:

They were quite difficult discussions. They were not easy discussions. Emotions were involved. Questions of race, sexuality, generate a lot of emotions.

In the context of these difficult discussions, in the late 1990s a number of Collective members resigned from the journal and there was some discussion about shutting it down. But the remaining editors decided instead to try to make the journal work with a different model. In the words of one of these women, this decision was taken:

² Gail Lewis, "Feminist Review: 25 Years and Beyond", *Feminist Review* 81, 1 (2005): 5–11. See also Avtar Brah and Celia Clini, "Open Space: Contemporary Feminist Discourses and Practices Within and Across Boundaries: An Interview with Avtar Brah", *Feminist Review* 117, 1 (2017): 163–70, and "Crisis of Care in the Feminist Review Collective" (2020), <https://femrev.wordpress.com/2020/08/04/crisis-of-care-in-the-feminist-review-collective/>

partly because the history of seventies feminism was that we had to go back and find feminist history, because it had been erased. So we had to join the dots up again. So one of my arguments was, if we drop the journal, then we would be dropping the baton. And we needed to keep it as a space where those debates and conversations kept going.

In the coming years, these same discussions that led to fundamental changes in the collective would influence the priorities established by the Trust. As one former collective and Trust member put it, by foregrounding issues of gender, race, ethnicity and sexuality the Trust, like the journal, “was trying to be intersectional before the term itself became current”.

What began at the turn of the millennium as an experiment in feminist solidarity on the part of a small group of feminist scholars developed over two decades into a well-respected independent feminist charity. But there were a number of hurdles along the way. Trustees struggled for years to get charity status; the Charity Commission rejected the FRT application at least twice, on the grounds that feminism was deemed “too political”. The law on this has now changed, and the FRT, like the LGBTQ+ charity Stonewall, was among the charities that benefited from this change. After Stonewall was finally recognised as a charity in 2003, the FRT hired the organisation’s solicitor to help with its own applications.

In June 2005 the Trust became a legal charity, with four core charitable objectives:

- 1) to advance the education of the public in the subject of gender by carrying out and/or assisting research and study into the social, economic and legal position of women in society, and to disseminate the results of such research and study;
- 2) to alleviate poverty and hardship by promoting and advancing good health and education amongst women in any part of the world;
- 3) to promote equality or opportunity between women and men in any part of the world;
- 4) to undertake other charitable purposes.

In addition to being ahead of its time as a recognised feminist charity, the FRT was one of a woefully small number of funders committed to providing money exclusively to activist projects directly affecting women. Women's organisations and feminist projects have always struggled to find adequate funding. For that reason, feminist charities have played a central role in both sustaining and directing feminist activism.

In spite of this, the history of feminism has paid relatively little attention to women's funding, in contrast to the impressive histories of women changing the world through direct advocacy and activism.³ This is perhaps not surprising. After all, marches, manifestos and music festivals make for more exciting stories than fundraising and cheque-writing. But the relative lack of interest in the history of feminist funding also suggests a discomfort with the issue of money, and an acute awareness that the questions of who has money to give, and who decides what kinds of issues and projects should be funded, are themselves highly political and potentially divisive.

In her study of feminist philanthropy in the United States between the late nineteenth century and the 1960s, Joan Marie Johnson argues that "the trajectory of the women's movement – its priorities, strategies, and successes – was deeply affected by the donations given by monied women". During this period, especially in the years before women were granted the suffrage, money was one of the few political tools that women could access. But it was a tool restricted to a few: a small number of wealthy, predominantly white women were able to use their capital to support a range of causes – a range that has remained remarkably consistent over almost two centuries: "political equality for women, assistance to working-class women and their children, educational and training opportunities, and reproductive rights".⁴ There was also a long and vibrant tradition of working-class and Black women's fundraising for education, health and other basic services in the context of limited and unequal public funding. But because those most able to donate to the mainstream women's movement were also the ones who called the shots, feminist philanthropy sometimes acted as a barrier to inter-class and inter-racial alliances among women.⁵

³ Joan Marie Johnson, *Funding Feminism: Monied Women, Philanthropy, and the Women's Movement, 1870–1967* (Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina Press, 2017), 2–3.

⁴ Johnson, *Funding Feminism*, 222.⁵ Johnson, *Funding Feminism*, 2–3.

The tension between the need for funding to drive and sustain feminist causes, on one hand, and the economic inequalities and financial power dynamics inherent to funding structures on the other, continues to condition feminist organising today. Returning to the US context, Johnson notes that in the early twenty-first century women still play a much more prominent role as volunteers than as donors within feminism. Furthermore, very little money comes from outside the movement: in the early twenty-first century, only 10% of major US funding foundations donate to women's organisations.⁶ This failure adequately to fund feminist projects extends to the global level. According to Lydia Alpízar Durán, former Executive Director of the Association for Women's Rights in Development (AWID), in the context of diminishing funding for women's organisations around the world, dedicated feminist funding foundations are crucial to supporting and enabling feminist work.⁷

Another AWID report, in 2015, found that in the first decade and a half of the millennium women's rights groups were dramatically underfunded relative to other kinds of organisation. While in 2010 large NGOs such as Save the Children or World Vision International had annual budgets of over US\$1 billion each, a survey of women's organisations around the world in the same period revealed that these operated on average on budgets of US\$20,000.⁸ Moreover, according to a 2019 *Guardian* article, only 1% of global funding for gender equality issues was going to women's and feminist organisations.⁹ AWID's assessment that "Women's rights organizations could be described as being in a state of survival and resistance" is an apt description of many of the feminist groups whose projects were funded by the Feminist Review Trust.¹⁰

⁶ Johnson, *Funding Feminism*, 14.

⁷ Angelika Arutyunova and Cindy Clark, *Watering the Leaves, Starving the Roots: The Status of Financing for Women's Rights Organizing and Gender Equality* (Association of Women's Rights in Development, 2013).

⁸ Lydia Alpízar Durán, "20 Years of Shamefully Scarce Funding for Feminists and Women's Rights Movements", 13 May, 2015;

<https://www.awid.org/news-and-analysis/20-years-shamefully-scarce-funding-feminists-and-womens-rights-movements>.

⁹ Kasia Staszewka, Tenzin Dolker and Kellea Miller, "Only 1% of gender equality funding is going to women's organisations – why?", *Guardian*, 2 July 2019;

<https://www.theguardian.com/global-development/2019/jul/02/gender-equality-support-1bn-boost-how-to-spend-it>.¹⁰ Durán, "20 Years of Shamefully Scarce Funding".

PROJECTS

There was a real openness to thinking about what feminism is.

FR Trustee

The Trust recognised from the start that the word “feminist” is dynamic and contested, always subject to different meanings and interpretations. An early Trust document recognised in particular that the meaning of the word had evolved in the two decades since the founding of the *Feminist Review* journal in 1979: “At that time the use of the word ‘feminist’ was both less contentious and less narrow than it is in 2001.”

The journal whose profits will be donated to the proposed Charity was established in the late 1970s and first published in 1979. Since its initial publication Feminist Review has established itself as a major international academic journal. ... Feminist Review is not in any sense a campaigning journal. Rather it is devoted to serious, academic scholarship.

FR Trustee

Because it had grown out of a scholarly journal, the Trust was originally envisioned as an academic charity to provide funding for feminist research and knowledge dissemination. Over the years this objective was refined, and by the time the Trust began to fold in 2021 it was funding largely non-academic women’s organisations from outside the UK.

Over the twenty-year period it operated (2003–2023), the FRT received tens of thousands of applications and funded 188 projects worldwide (see below, p.15). In the early years, most grantees received £1000 or less. Until about 2007, the majority of applications came from the UK, and many of these were requests for small grants for academic research projects (including some PhD research). Over the years, the geographical scope of applicants increased. In total, up to 2021, the FRT’s funding covered all continents, albeit not evenly: 16 projects in Africa; 12 each in Asia and the Middle East / North Africa; 17 in Latin America and the Caribbean; 3 in the USA; and 28 in continental Europe. A total of 75 projects, or about 40% of all grants, were based in the UK (most in England, a small number in Scotland, one in Northern Ireland, and a number covering the UK as a whole).¹¹

¹¹ Eleanor O’Gorman, “Funding Feminist Change – 20 Years of Action & Solidarity by the Feminist Review Trust: An Independent Learning Review” (2023).

In addition to expanding its geographical scope, the Trust began to make calls for applications in various priority areas: women with disabilities, LGBTQ+ organisations, violence against women and girls. As word of the Trust spread through feminist channels in particular countries, Trustees also actively sought to expand the geographical spread of applications, for instance to non-OECD countries. Over the years the size of maximum grant likewise increased. Nevertheless, the amount of funding available remained relatively small. The largest grant given was £15,000, and fewer than fifteen applicants received £10,000 or more. The smallest grant was for £300. Most awards were between £1000 and £9500. In other words, the Trust spread its limited funds (between £20,000 and £50,000 per year from the profits of *Feminist Review*) to as many recipients as possible, while prioritising innovative projects that would make a real difference to women's lives.

By the end of the Trust's first decade, as the number of international applications increased, the balance between funding for academic research and grassroots women's organisations and initiatives was beginning to shift. As one newer Trustee with experience in the funding sector noted, the FRT was in a valuable position to fund smaller, local organisations because it could get money to those groups directly, through legal means, but without the onerous and time-consuming bureaucracy required by most of the larger funders. At the same time, the Trust also funded a small number of established feminist charities and NGOs in the UK and abroad.

When deciding which projects to fund, Trustees put an emphasis on what one Trustee called "viable activist" projects.

This year we have had two priorities: activist activities and core funding. Activist activities have long been a priority but this year we decided to give more support to core funding. Most organisations find it very difficult to raise core funding. Most donors want to support a particular project. We felt the FRT should therefore be more sympathetic to core funding requests. We have discussed whether we should become more strategic in this regard and identify organisations we would like to support and then invite applications, but we decided against this for the moment.

Feminist Review Trust meeting minutes, 2011

Another reason for deciding on a set of priorities was the desire to streamline the process of choosing what to fund from an ever-growing number of applications. Trustees therefore

agreed upon a series of key themes, and encouraged applications based on these. Three examples of the themes chosen over the years are migrant women, disabled women and LGBTQ+ projects. While announcing priorities via the website did lead to receiving some more applications in these areas, overall the focus of the applications increasingly reflected the remit of big international funders. For example, when UN Women announced gender-based violence as a major global priority around 2018, the numbers of applications focused on violence against women and girls increased notably. As one Trustee recalled:

As more funders became interested in feminist issues, projects became more stereotypical: income-generating projects; domestic violence; millennial goals. Once the FRT got onto the generalised list there were more run-of-the-mill applications.

As another put it, “The world moved on; millennial goals kicked in.”

The Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) were a set of eight objectives laid out by the United Nations in 2000:

1. Eradicate extreme poverty and hunger
2. Achieve universal primary education
3. Promote gender equality and empower women
4. Reduce child mortality
5. Improve maternal health
6. Combat HIV/AIDS, malaria and other diseases
7. Ensure environmental sustainability
8. Global partnership for development¹²

Only one of the eight goals (number 3) mentions gender and women directly, while a second (number 5) references women in their capacity as mothers.

The projects funded by the Trust both reflected and departed from the main trends in international feminist funding. While the MDGs and other priorities set by international charities and NGOs had some impact on the kinds of application the Trust received, the FRT’s criteria for selecting successful applications also changed over the years, based on lessons learned about what kind of funding worked well and what was less successful. Additionally, the Trust’s priorities were less predictable than those of the big NGOs,

¹² See <https://research.un.org/en/docs/dev/2000–2015>.

reflecting the changing concerns of academic and activist feminisms at national and international levels. Although there was some overlap between the focus of projects funded by the Trust and those supported by other women’s funds – including programmes related to what we might call “traditional” transnational feminist issues, notably violence against women and reproductive rights (including abortion and maternal health)¹³ – the Trust was particularly innovative in giving money to hard-to-fund projects, explicitly political projects (including those that aimed to change the law) and those that are controversial among larger charities (including some feminist funders): sex workers’ rights, LGBTQ+ issues and abortion.

But perhaps most importantly, even though it actively sought applications in hard-to-fund areas, the Trust remained committed to supporting risk-taking and innovative proposals.

We tried to find the right kind of project within these themes. The themes themselves could become a fetish.

FR Trustee

The emphasis on originality as well as viability was one of the reasons Trustees dedicated so much care, time and work to shortlisting and selecting successful applications – and why, despite its relatively low level of funds, the FRT managed to support such an impressive range of programmes and organisations over the years.

¹³ According to an AWID survey of 37 women’s funds around the world, published in 2014, the top two categories of women’s issues funded by women’s funds at the start of the second decade of the twenty-first century were 1) economic, social and cultural rights (29%) and 2) gender-based violence/violence against women (27%). Reproductive rights was no. 6 of 10. Arutyunova and Clark, *Watering the Leaves, Starving the Roots*, p. 87.

Feminist Review Trust Awards by Theme (numbers of projects)¹⁴

¹⁴ Courtesy of Eleanor O’Gorman, “Funding Feminist Change”.

Thematic areas	Projects funded with this theme
Violence against Women & Girls	36
Arts & Culture	28
Migrant & Refugee Women	27
Running Feminist Groups/Centres	18
Health-focused Projects	17
Abortion and Sexual & Reproductive Rights	15
Memory, Narratives, & Oral Histories	13
Women with Disabilities	9
Economy & Work	8
Education-focused Projects	7
Justice Processes & Systems	7
Journalism & Media	7
Peace & Conflict	6
Sex Workers	6
Environment & Climate Change	3
Total	207

¹⁵ This table is based on the 177 projects funded by the Trust until 2021. (An additional 11 projects were funded between 2022 and the Trust’s final closure in 2023, making a total of 188.) The overall total of 207 projects in this table reflects the fact some of the 177 funded projects included here addressed more than one theme. The thematic analysis allocated a project more than one label if it addressed different themes

Feminist Review Trust Awards by Theme (percentages)

As the above table and pie chart demonstrate, the Trust’s largest area of thematic support was Violence against Women and Girls, making up 18% of the 177 projects funded between 2003 and to 2021. Other major themes included: Arts & Culture, Migrant & Refugee Women (14% and 13% respectively); Running Feminist Groups/Centres, Health-related Projects, Abortion and Sexual & Reproductive Rights (9%, 8% and 7% respectively); and Memory, Narratives, & Oral Histories (6%). Smaller but still distinct

themes included Women with Disabilities and Economy & Work (each 4%); Education-focused Projects, Justice Processes and Systems, Journalism and Media, Peace & Conflict, and Sex Workers (each 3%); and finally, Environment & Climate Change (2%).

The Trust's specialism in funding difficult-to-fund and innovative areas of feminist activism is revealed in comparisons with other global funders focused on women's and girls' issues. For example, in the second decade of the twenty-first century, gender-based violence was the top priority among women's funders globally, receiving over a quarter of total funding; similarly, almost one fifth of Trust projects focused on combatting violence against women and girls. Not far behind came funding for artistic and cultural projects and events – another area prioritised by many international feminist funders. In contrast, support for women migrants and asylum seekers, which made up about the same percentage of Trust projects as those focused on arts and culture, does not feature as a top-ten priority in AWID's 2014 survey of thirty-seven women's funds around the world. The Trust's support for migrants and refugees suggests a broad understanding of feminism, one that goes beyond conventional "women's issues", and also reflects what one founding Trustee (cited above) stressed was the Trust's commitment to intersectional feminism (that is, feminism that prioritises attention to the ways in which relations of gender intersect with, reinforce, and are reinforced by those of race, class, sexuality, and disability).

The decision to fund a total of twenty-seven programmes (on average more than one per year) addressing migrant rights and solidarity reflects both a growing academic and activist interest in these issues (as evidenced, for example, in the pages of *Feminist Review*)¹⁶ and a need to counter the growing attacks on migration and migrants' rights around the world. The Trust gave money to a number of UK-based organisations supporting women migrants and asylum seekers – including those detained under the country's increasingly brutal asylum laws; but funding was also provided for migrant and refugee support groups in Eastern and Southern Europe, Africa, the Middle East and Asia. Many of these projects were specifically aimed at meeting the needs of survivors of gender-based violence and torture, lesbians, and girls and young women.

¹⁶ See, for example, the special issue "Gendering Diaspora", *Feminist Review* 90 (2008).

Bail for Immigrant Detainees (2006)

Over its twenty years, the Trust funded a number of projects related to women, migration and asylum, both in the UK and abroad. These included:

- Facilitating Justice for Traumatized Women Seeking Asylum (2012)
- Gendering Asylum Protection Systems (Italy, 2014)
- Support for Women Refugees in Camp in Chios, Greece (2018)
- Migrant Women and Gender-based Violence (2018)

Requests for, and decisions to fund, these projects reflected both a growing area of concern in feminist activism and scholarship around migration and gender, and the worsening political and legislative situation vis-à-vis migration in the UK and internationally during the first two decades of the twenty-first century.

Migrant support organisations made funding bids in response to these changes, in an attempt to challenge increasingly anti-migrant discourses and practices, an environment infamously captured in 2012 when then Home Secretary Theresa May boasted about the UK government creating a “hostile environment” for migrants.

In 2006 the organisation Bail for Immigrant Detainees (BID), a charity, still operational today, that provides free legal support to detainees challenging their detention, received FRT funding “to conduct research into use of detained fast-track asylum processes for women at Yarl’s Wood Immigration Removal Centre”. Yarl’s Wood had been opened under the Labour government five years earlier, in 2001. Run by the private security firm SERCO, it remains the largest migrant detention centre for women and families in the UK. Over the past twenty years, Yarl’s Wood has become synonymous with the harsh treatment of those seeking to migrate to the UK, including women and children seeking asylum.

In February 2005 the Labour government published its New Asylum Model (NAM), which included the target of fast-tracking up to 30% of asylum applications under the Detained Fast Track (DFT) system. DFT was first introduced for men seeking asylum in 2003, and in 2005 was extended to women in Yarl’s Wood. Under DFT, people seeking asylum would have their cases heard and decided while they were interned at Yarl’s Wood.

BID proposed to conduct the first detailed research into this new accelerated asylum procedure. FRT funding paid for BID volunteers to travel to asylum review hearings for the purpose of observation and to interview former detainees. BID’s final report, *Removal Factory*, presented evidence from “31 cases decided in detention, including women who have fled sexual abuse, torture, and domestic violence”. The research incorporated evidence given by women from Sri Lanka, Uganda, Cameroon, Guinea, Somalia, India, Ethiopia, Sierra Leone, DRC, Pakistan, Burundi and Togo.

In their final report to the FRT, BID stressed that “The research funded by the Trust found that women’s ability to prepare and present their asylum claims is fundamentally undermined by the detained fast track.” As a result, there was a notable gap between the failure rate for

asylum applications heard outside detention (83%) and those heard while the claimants were held in Yarl's Wood (99%).

Ultimately, DFT was too fast to address complex cases. The report concluded that decisions on who would be granted asylum were largely arbitrary; high refusal rates were likely connected to a lack of preparation time. Furthermore, only two thirds of women claimants had legal representation (in contrast to the Home Office, which always had lawyers to make its case). Furthermore, there was almost no monitoring of DFT.

Refusal Factory: Women's Experience of the Detained Fast Track Asylum Process at Yarl's Wood Immigration Removal Centre was published in September 2007 and widely disseminated, including to the National Coalition of Anti-Deportation Campaigns, refugee legal groups, the UK Home Office, the Ministry of Justice, the Prison Service, legal groups, and Members of Parliament. The report was launched at an event at Toynbee Hall in London. Two women formerly detained in Yarl's Wood were among the speakers, and several others attended the launch event.

The aim of *Refusal Factory* was to draw attention to the unjust process underway at Yarl's Wood and its impact on women asylum seekers in particular. The authors and BID aimed to use the report's evidence to lobby and campaign for changes in policy and practice, so that women asylum seekers would have fair hearings and a fair chance of winning their cases.

Refusal Factory also provided important testimony to the lives and experiences of women seeking asylum in the UK in the early twenty-first century, as these three comments from women illustrate:

I don't understand the process. I don't know the rules, so I don't know if I'm following the rules.

No, the system is not fair. There is not enough time for women to explain themselves. Anything you say, they tell you is a lie. The Immigration Service is very rude; they don't want to listen to you. There are lots of traps. They are biased and inconsiderate.

Fast track is just a system to refuse people. There is no time to listen to you. Even the judge didn't listen. When they put you in fast track there is [only] a very small chance to get out. I never heard of one person who won a fast track case in one year. How can everyone be lying?

Since its publication in 2007, *Refusal Factory* has been widely cited by other migrants' rights organisations and by academics researching migration and asylum in the UK and transnationally, especially in relation to the gender politics of migration and asylum.

In 2015, the High Court deemed DFT to be unlawful, "systematically unfair and unjust". However, in 2021 the Conservative government's new policy statement on immigration aimed "to ensure the asylum and appeals system is faster and fairer". Critics interpreted this as a *de facto* return to the old fast-track system under a new name.

In 2018, the Feminist Review Trust funded a different charity working with asylum seekers: Yarl’s Wood Befrienders, an organisation providing volunteer support and services for women detained indefinitely at the detention centre. Their activities included organizing weekly sessions with detained women, providing refreshments, and activities run by volunteers, as well as basic services and provisions such as clothing, underwear, shoes, suitcases, money to access medical notes and phone top-up (BID had itemised how the funding would be allocated – but the FRT adjusted this slightly, increasing the amount for phone top-up). This funding was one example of the Trust stepping in to provide basic facilities and support that should have received government money, a reflection of both the persistence of the “hostile environment” and the lack of public funds for essential provisions for some of the most marginalised women in the UK.

Given the global context in which migration is increasingly dangerous and too often deadly, feminist research and support work on migration can often feel like a one-step-forward, two-steps-back scenario. But another way of interpreting the significant work done in this area, to which the FRT made a small but significant contribution, is as evidence of the strength of transnational and national networks of feminist solidarity in the face of increased hostility against migrants and people seeking asylum around the globe.

The Feminist Review Trust further stood out from most women’s rights funding bodies in deliberately seeking to finance smaller community-based and grassroots projects – including local feminist centres in different parts of the world – and by targeting funding for lesbians, women of colour and disabled women. Over the years, the Trust also funded six projects explicitly engaged with the rights of sex workers – a particularly difficult-to-fund issue in the context of a global turn towards campaigns to criminalise sex work among many mainstream feminist organisations.¹⁷ In addition, the Trust funded two restorative justice projects, a number of projects in support of women in prison (in the UK and in Mexico) and six projects working with women in conflict zones around the world, including Asia, the Middle East and Latin America.

¹⁷ See E Ward and G. Wylie, eds. *Feminism, Prostitution and the State: The Politics of Neo-Abolitionism* (London and New York: Routledge, 2019).

Ruta Pacífica Colombia Radio (2020)

Colombia has been in a situation of protracted conflict since the mid-twentieth century. The causes of violence in the country are complex and historical: economic, social, religious and political differences dating back to independence in the nineteenth century; state-sponsored paramilitary wars against leftist guerrillas since the 1960s; and the US-led war against cocaine production (Plan Colombia) in the 1980s. In 2016, Colombia's largest guerrilla group, the FARC (Revolutionary Armed Forces of Colombia) signed a permanent peace accord with the Colombian government. However, violence against civilians by both dissident guerrilla groups and right-wing paramilitaries persisted after the ceasefire. Moreover, the second decade of the twenty-first century was "marked by the decrease in women's rights ... and disinformation on gender, peace and rights issues" (Trust Funding Application from Colombian Women's Peaceful Route [Ruta Pacífica de las Mujeres], 2020).

Decades of conflict also gave rise to a strong citizens' peace movement, with women at the forefront. In 1996, the Ruta Pacífica de las Mujeres (RPM) was founded as part of the Colombian Citizens' Movement for Peace (Movimiento Ciudadano por la Paz). RPM is a "feminist, pacifist, anti-militaristic organization committed to an ethic of nonviolence". The organisation's founding principles are justice, peace, equality, autonomy, liberty and recognition of the other. By the time of the 2016 peace accord, RPM had established a network throughout Colombia of over 300 grassroots movements and organisations formed by women from diverse backgrounds: Indigenous, Afro-Colombian, peasants, urban workers, youth, university students, graduates and intellectuals. The organisation's "social base is the working-class women from barrios in towns and major cities across Colombia who, along with peasants and the internally displaced, have suffered most harshly the impacts of the armed conflict".

Since the 2016 ceasefire, RPM has continued to work with other peace organisations in Colombia to ensure a full and lasting post-conflict transition, with the voices of women fully incorporated. In the words of scholar Kate Paarlberg-Kvam, "The years following the Colombian Congress' 2016 approval of peace accords with the country's oldest and largest guerrilla army have brought into stark relief Cynthia Enloe's assertion that 'wars don't simply end, and wars don't end simply'".¹⁸ As comparative studies of conflict and transitions to

¹⁸ Kate Paarlberg-Kvam, "What's to come is more complicated: feminist visions of peace in Colombia", *International Feminist Journal of Politics* (2018); <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616742.2018.1487266>; p. 1.

peace have demonstrated time and again, such processes often leave women out of the picture, and rarely consider the multiple ways in which armed conflict is gendered. Mainstream peace processes frequently also fail to draw on feminist knowledge and resources to construct a post-conflict society free from all forms of violence, including interpersonal and gender violence. One of RPM's aims is thus to ensure "that women become political actors not only as victims of war, but as participants in the implementation of the peace accords and the construction of a long-lasting peace".

Three years after the 2016 ceasefire, RPM applied to the Feminist Review Trust for funding to produce a weekly radio programme: Lunas y Amaneceres (Moons and Dawns). The hope was "to strengthen the capacities of women and their organizations, through the use of radio as a communication tool, for the dissemination of their stakes invested in the peace process and the guarantee of their rights, in order to be recognized as subjects of rights and builders of peace in Colombia", and to provide journalistic training to ten young women journalists.

Prior to applying to the Trust, RPM had made some eighteen episodes of Lunas y Amaneceres, which were broadcast by the Industrial University of Santander throughout the metropolitan area of Bucaramanga, the municipalities of Soto Norte and in San Gil and Sur de Bolívar. The aim of the FRT funding was to produce further programmes to be disseminated more widely throughout the country through community radio stations and digitisation, in the process creating and expanding “strategic advocacy space to sensitize and generate a critical mass in favour of peace and women's rights in the most rural areas of north-eastern Colombia”. This region has one of the highest rates of violence against women in the country and is a priority area for the implementation of the peace agreement.

The radio episodes produced by RPM focused not only on the impact of conflict and political and state violence on women and women’s roles in the process of peace and reconciliation, but also on wider issues related to gender and women’s socio-economic status in Colombia: the economy of care, domestic labour, informal work, children’s labour and children’s rights, intrafamilial violence, the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic, humanitarian childbirth, reproductive rights, women in the national strike, sexual violence as a weapon of war, the environment, fatherhood, police violence, love as a political act, Afro-Colombian women and conscientious objection.

Lunas y Amaneceres

HOY
10 de junio, 10 a.m. por
UIS AM - 670 Khz.

Tema:
**Violencia sexual
como arma de guerra**

Invitada:
María Fernanda Arboleda
fundadora de Petra Mujeres Valientes

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Lunas y Amaneceres

HOY
24 de junio, 10 a.m. por
UIS AM - 670 Khz.

Tema:
Medio Ambiente

Invitados:
Luisa Acuña Corporación COMPROMISO
Oscar Valderrama Ondas de Mortiñal

feminist review | TRUST

A number of the episodes produced by RPM are available in Spanish on Soundcloud: <https://soundcloud.com/rutapacificam>

This project was an example of how the Feminist Review Trust, as a small feminist funder, was able to provide targeted money for a specific project – the production of a series of radio programmes – to an organisation that receives general funding from larger non-governmental funders, in the process making an important impact in an area related to women’s cultural production, and providing job training in journalism to young women.

Another innovative aspect of many Trust-funded projects was the emphasis on preserving women’s and feminist history – a commitment that also reflected the FRT’s academic origins. The Trust gave grants to several oral history projects, focusing on lesbians in Bosnia and

Herzegovina, Black women in the UK, Rape Crisis Scotland and women and menopause. Other organisations received money to archive and preserve activist memory, such as the Archive of Sex Workers' Memory in Argentina (2021). Still others combined public history with cultural events, such as a Suffragette Festival in East London (2014) and an exhibition of Women in World War I (2013). In fact, almost one in six projects funded by the Trust involved the creative arts and culture: from theatre workshops with former prisoners in London and a feminist art space in Georgia to a mural dedicated to domestic workers in Mexico and a filmmaking group of queer people of colour in Glasgow.

Digital Desperados (2013) and Chicha Morada (2018)

Over the years, the Trust funded a number of feminist cultural projects: research for a production of *The Female Gaze* by disabled artist Sarah Gonnet (2019); using art to explore mental health issues in UK Pakistani and Bangladeshi communities (2018); preparation for a Sonic Cyberfeminisms conference (2016); support for SPERO: A Feminist Art Studio in Tbilisi, Georgia (2008), and several others. These projects highlighted the power of different kinds of art, performance and media to engage with feminist issues and promote change.

In 2013, the Trust provided money to **Digital Desperados**, a collective of queer filmmakers of colour based in Glasgow.

The collective's main aims were:

- to empower the creativity of women of colour;
- to break down the barriers which prevent women of colour from making their own films;
- to be part of creating a rich creative culture where everyone can experiment with expressing their ideas, opinions, and visions, furthering their artistic development;
- to create public events which encourage cultural diversity and respect between people with different life experiences;
- to be part of creating a world free of racism and sexism.

Digital Desperados also ran the Glitch Film Festival in Glasgow between 2015 and 2017, showcasing films by queer, trans and intersex people of colour.

Trust funding was used to provide a free filmmaking course for women of colour. As part of the course, eight women from Scotland, other parts of the UK and abroad made their own films and screened them at Glasgow's Centre for Contemporary Arts. The films were also uploaded onto Vimeo, and some were shown at national and international film festivals. A number of participants testified to the value of the course:

Going from zero knowledge of final cut pro to relative comfort using the program was extremely satisfying. I'm grateful for the opportunity to be exposed to great activists and speakers who came to screenings and held panels, it really enriched the course and my own thinking and writing. I'm grateful that there was so much space in the course for discussions among the participants; the ideas we exchanged as a group were playful, stimulating, brilliant! I also really valued being able to consult with the DD team as I was making my film, they offered such valuable ideas and advice.

It was really inspiring to be introduced to so many women of colour, queer film-makers and artists that I hadn't come across before, via the course and by the other DDers. I felt I could let my guard down on the course and just focus on making my film, exploring things that interest me and having a good time with the others.

The fact that the course was only for women of colour was entirely welcome. Not enough space/time/energy is given to women of colour. We have needs/issues that mainstream (mostly white, cis-gendered people) do not appreciate because they are privileged and do not have to deal with them every day. In addition, it has made me realise how much I love being in the company of other women of colour; so much need not be said because we come from the same spaces.

Another example of the creative use of visual media was the project **Chicha Morada**, a series of short videos featuring two young feminists in Lima and hosted by the independent Peruvian media outlet Wayka. The videos covered serious issues – violence against women, sexual harassment, migration, racism – using humour and a didactic approach. The programmes were presented and produced by an all-women team, “seeking to visualize stereotypes, everyday machismo (*micromachismos*) and various degrees of violence exercised against women”.

According to one of the presenters, Gabriela Modesto, Chicha Morada was one of the first feminist social media endeavours in Peru run by independent media. Most of the shows' viewers were between 18 and 35.

The first video in the series poked fun at the advice on “how to be feminine” given to women by traditional family-rights groups in Peru. Subsequent shows included an interview with a feminist Congresswoman on the difference between “femicide” and “homicide”, and why, contrary to sensationalist media reports, migration from Venezuela was not responsible for the increase in feminicides in Peru.

Chicha Morada had about 2000 followers when it ran in 2018. Unfortunately, when the project ended, the team was not able to secure funding to make more videos; but the videos are still available on [YouTube](#) and have been viewed by some 2500 people.

Like many of the cultural projects funded by the Trust, Digital Desperados and Chicha Morada provided opportunities for women and LGBTQ+ people to participate directly in the production of feminist art and education and to develop new skills and reach new audiences,

whether in cinemas or online, leaving their own feminist digital footprint even after their respective projects ended.

In the assessment of one Trustee, the FRT's uniqueness lay precisely in the fact that it was a small UK-based charity that gave money to feminist organisations around the world, including many outside Europe. The Trust specialised in funding very small groups that were able to make a big difference with very little money. In that sense, there was a significant divergence between the amounts awarded and the impact of the projects. As this same Trustee put it, "We reached really deep down into local communities – these things distinguish the FRT from other feminist funder"

WORK

I joined the board because I was particularly impressed by the model that the Trustees adopted to change what they don't like about the world. It was a proactive and hands-on approach. They challenged patriarchy though academia and with the proceeds they supported small, hard-to-fund projects to complement the impact. It is true to form and exemplary of how feminists make change, diversify their tools and keep working towards their values.

FR Trustee

The founding members of the FRT were academics and members of the *Feminist Review* Collective. The Trust operated largely independently of the journal, although it received annual updates of its work and there were always two members of the FR collective acting as Trustees.

Trustees were appointed for three-year, renewable terms: as more were invited to join – including from outside academia – they brought a breadth of new and valuable experience, including in local government, grassroots activism and the voluntary and charity sectors. New Trustees also brought expertise in different parts of the world, knowledge of local and transnational NGOs, and contacts with feminist organisations and activists abroad who could, when needed, provide advice on specific applications. Some had been active in reproductive rights, peace and conflict or LGBTQ+ politics; others were specialists in different geographical areas, including Latin America, Africa and the former USSR.

In short, the Trust was made up of highly skilled women who were experienced in negotiating contracts, setting up charities, controlling large public-sector budgets, running big academic departments and heading up NGOs. Trustees were part of global networks across regions such as Africa and South Asia, and were experienced in negotiating with national and global institutions including the Department for International Development, the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund, as well as supporting feminists around the world who were endangered by their political activism.

The Trust was an example of how global feminist networks work.

As the expertise and reputation of the Trust grew, so too did the work of the Trustees.

Before the FRT was granted charitable status in 2005, it typically received under twenty applications per funding round. This number gradually rose to sixty applications per round – a manageable number for the small board. In this early period, one Trustee was assigned to draw up a shortlist of potential grantees, after which the board would go through the applications together to assess the applications collectively and choose which projects to fund. An undated early document explained this process to applicants:

Decisions about Awards are made by the Trustees. The Trustees meet three times each year. They may occasionally decide about applications outside this time frame but only in exceptional circumstances.

When applications are received, they are read and typically about one third will be shortlisted. These shortlisted applications are read in detail by all the Trustees and are also sent to a panel of external referees. Your references may be contacted at this stage.

Following the Trustee's meeting you will be notified of the Trustee's decision. If you have been successful you will be sent a Grant Acceptance Form, a Final Report Form and a copy of the Trust logo. Subject to the satisfactory completion of the Grant Acceptance Form your award will be released.

The Trustees are unable to enter into correspondence about the reasons for their decisions. Most applications fail to win support simply because we receive so many applications that we are unable to fund them all and therefore have to make some very difficult decisions.

As word spread of the Trust's reliability in funding small, successful and hard-to-fund grassroots projects, the number of applications increased dramatically. By the time it announced its closure in 2021, the Trust was receiving up to 1,500 - 2000 applications per year, a substantial increase over just two decades. This increase in demand for funding also required a revised working model.

While the Trust never established formal titles or roles, it did develop a de facto division of labour, with each Trustee taking on a specific job: longlisting and shortlisting applications, administering funds, doing the accounts, chairing meetings, communicating and following up with grantees, updating the website, and so on. In addition to her specific role, each Trustee took on a small number of shortlisted applications (about six) per funding round and was charged with reading and evaluating these. In order to assess the quality and viability of

each project, each Trustee researched her set of applications (one Trustee remarked, “I spent my life Googling”), contacted referees and, on occasion, consulted outside experts. Three times a year the Trust held meetings at which each Trustee presented the applications she had read and researched, making recommendations for funding or not. This was followed by a collective discussion and decision on which ones to fund – a decision which, given the Trust’s limited funds, also involved turning down what were undoubtedly some excellent and worthy projects.

The exact number of successful applications depended not only on their quality and viability, as well as the recommendations of referees, but also on the amount requested and the available budget in any given round. Some applicants received only part of the money they requested – for example, if the Trustees decided that certain aspects of a proposal were likely to receive funding elsewhere, or some elements were more urgent than others, or the proposed budget was out of the Trust’s funding range. In other cases, including those where it had proven difficult to track down referees, applications were deferred to the next round for decision after further investigation. Occasionally time was set aside at meetings to audit the profile of the Board of Trustees at the time – identifying gaps in knowledge, skills and experience – and to strategize for the recruitment of new Trustees.

In addition to meeting three times a year to select successful applications, the Trustees held an annual meeting at which they reviewed the work of the previous year. The Chair prepared a report on the categories of awards made and another Trustee prepared reports on the profile of applicants’ countries and the types of applications received, comparing these to the Trust’s changing list of priority areas. At this yearly meeting, Trustees would also evaluate the FRT’s priorities and make changes, including adding new categories.

Choosing whom to fund was only one stage in the process. Equally important and demanding were the tasks of contacting the successful applicants, communicating with them about their awards, getting the money to them, following up on their success and, in a number of cases, supporting them to make changes in order to make their projects more viable. A key aim here was to provide women’s organisations with the knowledge and skills they needed to make more successful funding bids in the future, since the Trust was rarely in

the position to provide follow-up or longer-term funding. For example, if a group with a great idea put forward unrealistic elements in their plan for the use of the award, they were encouraged to make alterations. In some cases, the dedicated Trustee would support the organisations with making their budgets. Additional time and effort were required when, for whatever reason (often a serious lack of staff or other resources), grantees were not able to complete their full project or meet deadlines. These situations multiplied dramatically during the Covid-19 pandemic, when the Trustee charged with communicating with grant holders took on the additional task of writing to all groups with current awards, expressing the Trust's concern for the impact on them and their activities, and Trustees' support and understanding that they might need to adjust their deadlines.

For this reason, notwithstanding the staggering amount of work involved, the decision-making process could also be tremendously satisfying, especially when it meant giving money to truly innovative projects. As one Trustee recalled: "Getting down to the projects worth considering properly felt like a real privilege".

Rojava Project (2015)

Four years after the outbreak of war in Syria, the Trust received a funding request from Weqfa Jina Azad a Rojava li Sûrî Bakûrê (WJAR, Foundation of Free Women of Rojava) to help provide non-patriarchal education to kindergarten children in Rojava, Northern Syria.

In addition to the Kurdish majority in Rojava, the region is home to Syriac, Assyrian and Armenian Christians, Yazidis, Turkmen and Chechens.

Since 2012, Rojava has been the site of ongoing conflict. The region gained autonomy following its liberation by Kurdistan Workers' Party (PKK) forces in 2012, and has since been the site of struggles against ISIS, regular invasions from Turkey, and an ongoing economic embargo by the Syrian government. Over the past decade, Rojava has also been engaged in a political project for ethnic and gender equality, as well as environmental justice, drawing volunteers and solidarity from all over the world. Projects in Rojava are particularly difficult to fund because of the ongoing embargo.

WJAR applied for Trust funding through the International Women's Federation in the Netherlands. One former Trustee recalls the wider context in which the WJAR kindergarten project was funded:

The Foundation of Free Women in Rojava (WJAR) submitted their

application to the Trust in 2015–16. The application proposed a feminist developmental framework for a kindergarten in Rojava whose practices aimed to challenge patriarchy, racism and economic exploitation. Rojava was liberated by the PKK and other Kurdish forces in 2012, when they claimed territory bordering Turkey in the north-east of the country for the Kurdish people. The struggle for Kurdish autonomy had long included women taking up arms. Eight years into the Syrian civil war the PKK worked with the Americans against ISIS, affording them some protection from continued Turkish aggression. As circumstances changed, however, the vulnerability of Rojava to Turkish hostility changed as well. The Trust application was submitted less than three years after Rojava declared its existence.

After we made the award of £9,000 some WJAR women came to London and asked to have a meeting with women from the Trust. Following our meeting I was even more aware of the predicament of people living in Rojava, constantly fearing for their safety as the war escalated, and worried the nursery would be bombed. But, in spite of persisting Turkish aggression, the women's project survived and strengthened. In the midst of this formative and ongoing context of war, the feminist nursery project continues to grow while global warfare swirls around them. Theirs is a remarkable achievement the Trust is proud to have played a tiny part in sustaining.

Before 2012, under Assad's regime in Syria, kindergartens had been used to assimilate (or Arabise) the Kurdish population. The WJAR project, in contrast, aimed to teach children in Kurdish and other mother tongues, promoting educational methods to enhance equality in the areas of gender, ethnicity and religion. The aim was for teachers to abandon the practice of rote teaching and memorisation that had been promoted under Syrian rule, in favour of a focus on children's self-determination, self-responsibility and positive development.

The target groups for the project were the children themselves, their teachers and the children's parents (most of the children lived in one-parent families, usually with their mothers). The project was carried out through a series of workshops with teachers and parents in kindergartens in the villages of Qamishlo and Derik. Through these workshops, organisers came to understand the extent to which children and families had been traumatised by the war, and a psychologist was also brought in to support the children and their parents.

An early reported challenge for the project was that some teachers had to overcome their prejudices against the parents, whom they assumed to be uneducated and poor, and therefore not in an ideal situation to raise their own children. Such attitudes led some parents to withdraw their children from school. This early experience of conflict in the programme in turn prompted the organisers to develop a system "which acknowledges care, love and culture of the families on one side and discusses the negative and positive effects of education of

children on the other side.”

By the end of the first stage of the project in 2016, organisers reported a series of successes:

- Development of trust and respect between teachers and parents; a process of self-reflection on the part of teachers helps them value the families’ cultures and principles;
- Personal development of children: they become “calmer and more balanced” and as a result more parents also send younger children to kindergarten; parents see the value of the project;
- Improved relationships between children and parents; less violence in families; empowerment of mothers and daughters in families;
- Effect of programme beneficial not only to children in the kindergartens but also other children in the families (each family typically has 6–12 children);
- Improvement in the relationship between different ethnic and religious groups in neighbourhoods where the families live.

The report further notes, “The establishment of the kindergartens was financed by the WJAR. The qualifying workshops of the kindergarten teachers by WJAR, co-financed by Feminist Review Trust, have also been recognized by the Ministry for Women of the Democratic Federation of North Syria and have been positively reviewed.”

By the time the FRT funding came to an end, the Ministry of Women of the Democratic Federation of North Syria had agreed to continue to pay for the training of teachers and parents, thus guaranteeing the project’s sustainability. This was an important example of FRT funding leveraging longer-term, more sustainable funding for a life-changing project in a difficult-to-fund area.

The Rojava project was one of a small number of projects that the Trust funded in conflict zones. Others included North Sri Lanka and Crimea. In 2020, the Trust once again funded a project in Northern Syria, this time to train women in journalism.¹⁹ This was also an example of a project on which the FRT collaborated closely with another international organisation to fund an innovative project that was very difficult to fund because of the ongoing conflict, embargo and geopolitical situation.

¹⁹ For more information on Rojava, including the kindergarten project, see <https://wjas.org/en/projects/kindergardens/>. See also <https://rojavainformationcenter.com/background/key-facts/>

CHALLENGES

The Trust continues to receive a large number of applications. Typically we received between £250 to 300k of applications each round despite a warning on the website about the small percentage that are successful. As ever, this indicates the huge paucity of funds to fund feminist activities. In the UK we fear that the cuts will only make this already difficult situation much worse.

FRT Minutes, July 2011

*How do you decide what should be funded in the interest of feminism?
Who gets to decide where funding for feminist work should go?*

FR Trustee

Like all feminist organisations, the FRT faced a number of challenges over the years. In part these were shaped by existing and external factors. The nature of funding bodies is such that they can fund only a fraction of the applications they receive: turning down and disappointing excellent proposals along the way comes with the territory. Decision-making on who gets money and who does not is all the more trying in a wider political and economic context in which, as noted above, feminist organisations are almost always strapped for cash, and many operate in openly hostile environments, in some cases in zones of violent conflict.

But some of the dilemmas and difficulties the Trust faced were the result of its particular working model, which in turn was shaped by the historical context out of which it grew and developed.

The work and effort that went into reviewing applications and making final decisions on who was to be funded was probably the Trust's single greatest ongoing challenge, one that increased along with the number of applications. One Trustee described the painstaking decisions that went into narrowing down hundreds of applications to a handful to be funded as "constantly negotiating that tightrope".

Another externally imposed challenge was giving equal treatment to applications that were often different in quality – not in terms of the proposed projects, but in terms of the written submissions. As anyone who has ever written a funding application – whether for an academic research project or a small feminist NGO – knows, drawing up a bid is time-consuming and painstaking work. Today most universities have entire departments with paid staff dedicated to supporting academics applying for external funding. For small, cash-poor organisations, especially those outside the global North, the process is not only onerous; it also takes place within an inbuilt bias in the funding system, one that favours organisations with existing resources to pay professional grant application writers, as well as those who can communicate easily in English. As one Trustee noted, applications from organisations based in Europe and/or academic applicants were often “slicker” than those that came from grassroots organisations in other parts of the globe.

The reality of a world in which women’s initiatives are underfunded and hundreds of groups compete for tiny pots of money is that organisations themselves have a tightrope to walk, balancing the desire to create and implement radical, innovative projects that will engage women and challenge existing power structures against the need to comply with the criteria set out by funders. On balance, even as it deliberately sought out applications in the former category, the Trust received more submissions for funding in the latter. The FRT encouraged risk, but many organisations feared that being bold and original carried the risk of failure. So they often stuck to tried, true and approved methods and themes such as the MDGs, cited above. One Trustee recalls that when the Trust announced its latest round of successful grantees, this was often followed by a flurry of “copycat” applications. Truly innovative projects were rare (but see, for example, some of the case studies included here, such as the Mammias initiative, Breastfeeding, Crisis and Inequalities, that opens this history, the Rojava kindergarten initiative related above and GAMCOTRAP, below).

Because the Trust prioritised focused and original proposals, it was more likely to take risks than some of the bigger funders. The strategy of giving preference to grassroots organisations was one way of guaranteeing a steady stream of imaginative applications, because those that were most likely to be original were the ones least embedded in state funding models. The Trust sometimes rejected projects that were viable and valuable but were likely to be able to get funding elsewhere. Trustees were also wary of funding larger

women's organisations that already received regular income from big NGOs, fearful that the Trust's commitment to funding actively feminist projects would be lost. But there were some notable exceptions. In a few cases the FRT did fund targeted, ground-breaking projects by organisations that received money elsewhere, such as GAMCOTRAP in The Gambia.

GAMCOTRAP (2012, 2014)

In 2012 the FRT awarded £10,000 – the largest available grant at the time – to the Gambia Committee on Traditional Practices Affecting the Health of Women and Children (GAMCOTRAP) to fund the pilot project entitled **Ending Female Genital Mutilation**.

Founded in 1984, GAMCOTRAP is a women's rights organisation working on the sexual and reproductive health and rights of women and girls in one of the least developed countries in the world (the Human Development Index ranked The Gambia 172 out of 187 countries in 2014). The country has a range of ethnic and linguistic communities, many based in small villages with limited access to outsiders.

The FRT-funded pilot project aimed specifically at empowering and enabling circumcisers (all women, many of them older women) to abandon the practice of female genital mutilation (FGM) in the country's Central River Region, North. In the context of the increasing commercialisation of FGM, circumcisers had become reliant on performing FGM to earn a living. The process of empowering circumcisers therefore had two steps: first, educating them through training sessions about the potential repercussions of FGM on women's and girls' sexual and reproductive health, as well as their human rights; and second, providing them with alternative forms of employment. In the words of the organisation, "The project was perceived as a feminist strategy to address the poverty of circumcisers who were supposedly providing services for the community."

The project grew out of observations made by workers during GAMCOTRAP's programmes in local communities and involved further direct involvement with these communities, including women and their families, local leaders (political and religious), and circumcisers. GAMCOTRAP also recognised the importance of involving men in the process of ending FGM.

During the FRT-funded pilot project, GAMCOTRAP gathered data on the lives and livelihoods of circumcisers during the first three months after they abandoned circumcision. In order to support the organisation in making successful bids in the future and extending the pilots to other regions in The Gambia, in 2014 the Trust offered follow-up funding that would allow the organisation to collect longer-term data on the project outcomes for former circumcisers.

This next stage involved not only educating circumcisers and providing alternative forms of employment, but also educating wider communities about the potential harms of FGM. One

challenge was that, although most of the circumcisers lived in poverty, they enjoyed a degree of status within their communities. It was important, therefore, for women to find alternative forms of employment that would also hold prestige (this was one of the questions built into the assessment of the project's success).

According to the final report:

45.9 percent [of former circumcisers] are engaged in petty trading; 39.2 percent are in animal husbandry; 8.8 percent in soap making; and 6.1 percent in gardening/farming. In the URR, 41.4 percent of ex-circumcisers are still engaged in petty trading; 31.6 percent are in animal husbandry; 6.0 percent in soap making; pottery 2.6 percent; 7.9 percent emergency personal cost; tie and dye make up 2.6 percent; 5.3 percent reported that they bought machines for groundnut grinding and 2.6 percent were engaged in gardening/farming.

A number of these women provided testimony to the changes in their lives and livelihoods:

The role of TBA [Traditional Birth Attendant] that I now assume has given me even higher roles, respect and honour.

I have the support of my community. I am respected and honoured. Now I do not have to work tirelessly to care for FGM girls. I concentrate on my selling.

I appreciate the intervention and knowledge gained; good work has been done and there is education to promote children's health.

FGM is a deep-rooted practice and we should continue to educate people about the harmful effects. This is what I do when children are brought to me.

I am happy with my AEO [Alternative Employment Opportunity], it is sustaining me.

I feel free and confident; I am no longer anxious about the possibility of a child's death but now concentrating on the fabrics – tie and dye.

In order to bring the entire community into the project of ending FGM and supporting the former circumcisers, GAMCOTRAP organised Dropping of the Knife (DOK) celebrations on 25 November (a UN-designated day to end violence against women) in 2015, which were attended by "district chiefs, religious scholars, donor agencies and other dignitaries who were in attendance to offer their moral support".

The vast majority of the communities in which GAMCOTRAP operated (95%) reported that FGM had been abandoned entirely. In 2015, the practice was legally prohibited in The Gambia.

The GAMCOTRAP project was notable in at least three ways:

- It was an example of the Trust funding a targeted project for a large women's organisation with substantial finance from some big international funders, including UNICEF and Save the Children.
- It was an intervention in an area – FGM – that is often singled out by major funders, but with a distinctive focus. The financial and social support was directed not at girls and women who experience FGM, but instead at the circumcisers themselves. In this way violence against women, one of the most commonly funded women's issues in development, was approached as an issue that is embedded not just in “culture” or “tradition”, but in economic structures.
- Finally, this was a project where the impact of the funding was visible and traceable through direct engagement over the years with the project managers, who maintained ongoing communication with the Trust.

There's a social aspect to funding isn't there? Particularly in these bleak political years.

FR Trustee

The question of how to distribute a tiny amount of cash among hundreds of mostly small feminist organisations throughout much of the world is inseparable from the wider economic context in which the Trust operated. The very need for funding, indeed for feminism, derives from a grossly unequal distribution of resources. This inequality became more acute in and after 2008, with the global economic crisis. In the UK this was followed shortly by the introduction of austerity measures by the Conservative–Liberal Democrat coalition government, elected in 2010.

The impact of austerity on women's organisations was felt directly by the FRT. In its second decade, it began to receive more and more requests for core funding from UK-based groups that had lost their financing or had seen it drastically reduced. The Trust also received requests for “sticking plaster” funding – that is, small amounts of money that would help to sustain an organisation while it applied for more secure support. As public funding dried up throughout the UK, and the government withdrew public money for countless community projects, the Trust was also asked to support projects that should rightfully have received government funding. One example was the volunteers supporting asylum seekers held at the Yarl's Wood detention centre to meet basic needs, including food, clothing and phones (see above).

All these problems were exacerbated by the outbreak of the Covid-19 virus in 2020.

The final grants given by the Trust coincided with the pandemic. The Trustee in charge of communicating with grantees during this period spent a great deal of her time reiterating the Trust's commitment to its projects and negotiating extensions or changes to objectives where necessary.

The Trust worked mostly with grassroots organisations, not all of whom had bank accounts. One of the things many grantees valued about the FRT was that the money "just arrived", in the words of one recipient, free from the miles of red type typically required by mainstream funders. However, getting even small amounts of money to organisations could prove challenging. Some groups relied on third parties to transfer money, and others were located in conflict zones (e.g., Rojava and Colombia; see above). While it was rare for a group that had received Trust funding to fall off the map entirely, the fact that many relied on volunteer labour and/or existed in a sector with high turnover rates meant that updates and reports were sometimes delayed. Doing follow-up with grant holders was one of the most time-consuming aspects of the Trust's work, adding to the burden of activist work on the Trustees themselves. Records of the communication between Trustees and the organisations the Trust funded are testimony to the multiple challenges of feminist organising, especially in tight times.

The Trust's limited resources also determined to a large extent what kinds of project it could fund. For example, it was unable to support large infrastructure projects (e.g. building schools, roads, providing physical spaces for women's centres, etc.). As one Trustee with extensive experience in the area of development noted, infrastructure and building projects are among those that prove most significant and lasting to women and the communities they live and work in. Occasionally the Trust was able to provide funding for smaller construction projects, such as a disabled toilet for disabled women following the earthquake in Nepal.

Disabled Women in Nepal (2016)

During its second decade, the Feminist Review Trust identified as one of its priorities an increase in the number of applications for projects supporting women with disabilities.

In 2016, the Trust received a funding request from Gramin Mahila Sriajanshil Pariwar (GMSP), a long-established women-led community development group working to end violence against women and girls in the Sindhupalchowk district of Nepal. Sindhupalchowk is located in the hills north of Kathmandu and is an area with high levels of poverty. The region also experienced the migration of much of its male population to work overseas. Sindhupalchowk was at the epicentre of the April 2015 earthquake in Nepal.

In the wake of the earthquake, GMSP was one of the lead organisations coordinating aid in Sindhupalchowk, including psycho-social support for women and men. In this context, GMSP became aware of the barriers to disabled women's engagement with initiatives to support rural women. GMSP began working with Nepal's Disabled Human Rights Centre with the aim of becoming entirely disability-inclusive at every level.

The aim of the funding requested from the Trust was to set up three self-support groups for women with disabilities and to build an accessible toilet in the organisation's offices, as well as to provide other accessible features. The funding was facilitated through the Disability and Development Partners organisation, based in the UK, which worked closely with GMSP to ensure the project was carried out successfully. The project therefore required a significant amount of liaison on the part of the Trust, and the outcomes were largely successful (in spite of the fact that in the first instance the accessible toilet was installed in the wrong place).

According to GMSP's report, all immediate objectives of the funding were met:

- The three disabled women's self-help groups were set up, but they need additional tangible support (funds for livelihoods) to improve disabled women's lives, to sustain the groups themselves and to kick-start group savings and interloans for the future.
- Physical improvements (accessible toilet, etc.) have been made, as part of the much larger building works which were needed, and which are continuing.
- Disability awareness training has been undertaken, and a new, more disability-inclusive strategy developed, but its real impact can only be evidenced after the training is concluded, by the greater inclusion of disabled women in GMSP's organisation, strategy and activities.

Over the years, the Trust funded a small number of projects in support of women with disabilities, most of which focused on training, empowerment and self-support. The Nepal programme was unique in terms of FRT grants in that it provided educational and empowerment activities along with essential infrastructure, in the form of an accessible toilet and other accessible building features.

According to research conducted in the aftermath of the Nepal earthquake, even though there was an inclusive disaster risk management (DiDRM) in place, in practice “a dire lack of inclusive and accessible equipment and resources ... hindered the search and rescue (SAR) and relief efforts, which resulted in the slow recovery and rehabilitation of persons with disabilities”. Following the disaster, all people consulted by researchers who were involved in providing support to the worst-hit communities “reported problems with providing and managing accessible toilets and washing facilities in temporary shelters”.²⁰ Wheelchair users and women with disabilities were the most disadvantaged groups in this situation.

Another challenge for the Trust was that many of the applications it received were targeted at supporting women, but not necessarily in a way that would challenge unequal gender relations and structures. In this regard, the FRT ultimately faced the same dilemmas as any feminist funder: how to distinguish projects that might support individual women or small groups of women but were not ultimately transformative in a wider sense; how to avoid funding projects that ultimately helped to sustain rather than challenge existing hierarchies of gender, race, class, ability and other categories.

One of the reasons the Trust funded so many artistic and cultural projects may have been that these were most easily identifiable as “feminist”. They were often projects proposed by small organisations, typically of young women, who wanted to use art, theatre, film or digital media to challenge sexism, racism and other inequalities in creative ways. But there are risks involved in making judgements about what is “feminist” and what is not, or what kind of feminist project to support.

The question became less “What’s the difference between feminist and women’s [issues]?” and less about “Is this a small outfit that could flourish, even though it can’t do sustainability?”, and more “How on earth do we make a call on this application?” And then that involved actually researching the organisation in the process of shortlisting. FR Trustee

In the Western feminist context in which the Trust worked, the legacies of colonialism and feminism have fundamentally shaped debates about what, exactly, feminism is and should be. Throughout the years, Trustees engaged in discussions about the dangers of colonial feminism, especially in relation to applications from Western academics conducting

²⁰ S.B. Bista, P.P. Simkhada, K. Ross-Houle and R.J. Khatri, “Nepal’s Response to Earthquake 2015: Experience of Emergency Responders and Humanitarian Assistance providers in Inclusive and Accessible Humanitarian Assistance Delivery” (2018); <http://researchonline.ljmu.ac.uk/id/eprint/1075/3/>.

research on countries in the global South, or feminist organisations based in the North requesting funding to work with organisations in the South. As one Trustee observed, the funding sector itself “comes with a lot of its own colonial problems”. In that regard, the attempt to break with that model could be seen as a success in itself. “Anything that works to channel funds out of big Western organisations to smaller grassroots organisations is probably a good thing.”

The problems of class, colonialism and whiteness were also relevant to the inner workings of the Trust. Like the *Feminist Review* journal, the FRT began as a largely white and middle-class organisation. The profile of Trustees changed over the years, as more younger women, including more women of colour and feminists with expertise outside academia, joined. Furthermore, during its second decade especially, Trustees conducted review sessions that included critical evaluations of its approach and led the Trust to seek and prioritise applications aimed at challenging structural oppression based on race, disability and sexuality in particular.

But a number of Trustees, both older and newer, recognised that the model of selecting new members from a relatively privileged group of women (academic and other professionals, the majority white) tended to reinforce rather than challenge traditional power relations among women. In the words of one:

Funding things is good. But funding comes with a power dynamic, and we didn't ever really grapple with that. It's important to remember that there's power in having money and distributing it.

Although it had very little money compared to the big international charities, the Trust took seriously the principles of value for money, impact and sustainability. In particular, it was concerned to prioritise projects that would have some kind of life after the Trust funding was used up. While successful applicants had to have sustainability built into their applications, changing circumstances and the realities of doing feminist activism in a hostile world often meant that sustainability was difficult to track in practice. Moreover, as one Trustee noted, sustainability is not always viable or immediately obvious in cases of innovative projects: “to get stuff off the ground and over the line initially is risky”. For another Trustee, sustainability

itself could run counter to the ethos of the Trust, to its commitment to funding projects that were unlikely to get funding elsewhere. She gave an example:

We funded things like buying feminist books for Zimbabwe – this is something that has a long life, doesn't need to be replicated, it doesn't need to grow, we don't need to build the model and do it elsewhere. It's what that group of feminists wanted and needed and they got it. ... I am very pro the model that you don't need to prove that you'll be successful to get the grant. You need to prove that you'll try.

Another crucial question was the sustainability of the Trust itself. Indeed, one Trustee recalls that while the FRT always asked applicants to describe how a project would be able to continue after Trust funding ended, on at least one occasion an applicant asked the Trust about *its own* model of sustainability – that is, did the FRT have the resource capacity to sustain a successful project beyond a one-time grant? The Trust did occasionally provide follow-up grants for particularly successful projects. But the question also alerted Trustees to the importance of considering its own financial stability.

On one level, the Trust was fortunate in this regard: almost all its funding came from a regular donation of about £30,000 per year from the profits of subscriptions to the *Feminist Review* journal. For one Trustee, the hybrid model of working with the journal was the Trust's strength. But she also recognised its limitations:

We were sort of wedded to the Feminist Review itself, and when that project was beginning to flounder, and we were starting to have difficulties ... And we were all volunteers. This is the thing about volunteers, how much time and effort can you put in? It would have involved a lot of effort to get the whole thing funded from elsewhere.

As the number of funding applications increased, the Trust did explore other avenues to increase its income and curtail its reliance on the profits from *Feminist Review*. But it never had the resources to dedicate to a large-scale fundraising campaign. Nor did it receive large donations from individuals or estates. An important exception was a £25,000 donation in 2011 from the Irene Bruegel Estate to support the empowerment of women in poor countries, which was used to fund projects in Kenya, Uganda and The Gambia.²¹ Trustees were also aware of a number of supporters leaving substantial sums to the Trust in their wills – gifts of support the Trust did not live long enough to receive.

Although the regular money from the journal allowed Trustees to focus attention on processing applications and allocating funds to feminist projects, this model also meant that it was entirely reliant on one source of funding – one that eventually disappeared when the *Feminist Review* collective did its own review of finances and spending priorities in 2021.

²¹ Irene Bruegel (1945–2008) was a socialist feminist researcher and activist involved in many campaigns to right injustices and empower the most vulnerable in society. The Irene Bruegel Bequest was used to fund a number of feminist projects: <https://www.feminist-review-trust.com/the-irene-bruegel-bequest/>.

ACTIVISM

*An enormous amount of care and labour and compassion
went into the Trust. FR Trustee*

*I look at the enormous amount of unpaid labour that went into whittling
down sometimes up to 600 applications to a handful of projects
in each funding round and wonder – Will this kind of model ever
be available again? FR Trustee*

Like that of the *Feminist Review* journal Collective, the Trust's working model was based on what one Trustee called an "ethos of collective working", one that allowed the Trust to donate almost all of its resources to other feminist organisations. This shared ethos was the organic link that kept the two entities working together for over twenty years.

Whether understood as part of a "feminist gift economy",²² activism, or volunteering, women's unpaid work has long sustained feminist organisations. All the Trustees consulted as part of this history project highlighted the challenges of balancing feminist activism with all the other demands in their lives: paid work, caring duties, securing stable housing, commitments to their wider communities. If anything, these challenges have increased by the third decade of the twenty-first century. The growing precarity and insecurity of younger feminists working in the university and voluntary sectors have made it unsustainable for many to invest time and energy in projects that do not provide a direct or potential income. In the words of one Trustee, who comes from a development and NGO background and joined the Trust in its later phase:

*It is important to include difficult questions about whether it is possible
any more to have the model of unpaid labour, whether this is a viable
model practically, politically and ethically.*

Another Trustee, who had joined the Trust earlier on, commented on the changes she had seen in terms of the ethos of collective unpaid work and the possibility of feminist activism from the time when the *Feminist Review* journal was founded in the late 1970s to the time when the Trust closed over forty years later:

²² Margaretta Jolly, "Purpose, Power and Profit in Feminist Publishing: An Introduction", *Women: A Cultural Review* 32, 3–4 (2021): 328.

We started outside the formal economy. Being outside the formal economy is only now available to people who are unencumbered by families and so on, who are able to do that. So volunteerism was, in my mind, solidly founded in what was feminism in the 1970s and 1980s. You gave it no thought. A large part of your practice was outside paid employment ... There were ways of living outside the market in the 1970s, squats etc., that just are not ... you know, everything has monetised. Everything. Everything has monetised to a great degree and everything costs a lot these days.

From the other end of the spectrum, one of the newer Trustees provided a different angle on this issue. For her the point is not that there are no young feminists willing to do unpaid activist work, but that their motivations are different. With so few entry-level jobs in the feminist not-for-profit sector, young people who want to enter that field have little choice but to start off working for free, in a system that reproduces the class hierarchies of the internship model:

If you were to set up something like the Trust now, entirely run by volunteers, volunteers would be early career, enthusiastic, desperate for experience for leverage into a paid job. Anyone who wants to work in social justice, or not-for-profit, is doing unpaid work at the start of their careers, which makes it completely inaccessible for lots of people. [It even] makes it very difficult for people who can [afford to work for free].

Abortion and Reproductive Rights

Few topics have featured as prominently in contemporary feminist activism as the struggle for reproductive justice.

Over the course of almost twenty years, the Trust received countless applications related to women's struggles to attain and maintain bodily autonomy and the right to abortion, and to spread awareness to women about their reproductive rights. This period – the first two decades of the twenty-first century – coincided with dramatic events around the world, from hard-won changes to the law in countries where abortion had long been restricted or banned (notably Argentina and Ireland) to the overturning of the landmark *Roe v Wade* decision in the United States in 2022, a judgement widely criticised for putting the reproductive rights and lives of low-income and other vulnerable women at particular risk.

The range of abortion rights projects funded over the years – from educational programmes to support for women with limited access to reproductive health services to

campaigns to counter anti-choice movements – highlights the ongoing importance of this issue, as reproductive rights continue to come under attack, especially in the context of the growing strength of right-wing movements around the world.

The A Word (Brienne LaBauve, 2004)

One of the Trust's early projects was *The A Word*, a documentary film by Brienne LaBauve that investigates the history of abortion law in Trinidad and Tobago dating back to the 1861 law under British rule and up to the campaigns for its reform in the early 21st century. The film was partly funded by the Trust and features a series of interviews with activists and others, looking into the role of the history of colonialism and religion, among other factors influencing debates around abortion. *The A Word* is available on [YouTube](#).²³

Advocates for Safe Parenthood: Improving Reproductive Equity: ASPIRE, Trinidad and Tobago: Respect My Choice Campaign (2007)

In 2007, the Trust funded a second project related to abortion rights in Trinidad and Tobago: Respect my Choice. The ASPIRE campaign invited people to its website (now defunct) to read stories about the impact of the country's abortion laws, to participate anonymously in forum discussions and to share their experiences. The stories included testimony from a woman who had had to hide two terminations from her husband and the account of a man whose girlfriend had died as a result of an illegal abortion. The aim was "to do what statistics can't: ... to generate compassion and inspire a search for common ground".

The impulse for the project was a campaign to gather support for the reform of laws on abortion, the leading cause of maternal morbidity in Trinidad and Tobago at the time. The project was established in the run-up to the country's elections in late 2007. Contributors were sought through advertisements in newspapers and on the radio, and some of the stories were also published in the country's main newspaper, the *Trinidad Express*, in September and October 2007, around the time of the Day of Decriminalisation of Abortion in Latin America and the Caribbean (27 September).

As of 2023, abortion remains illegal in Trinidad and Tobago, except in cases where it is deemed necessary to save the life of the mother.

Abortion Rights Pro-Choice Campaign (2007)

In 2007 the Trust provided funding for a campaign to mark the fortieth anniversary of the Abortion Act in Britain (1967), providing safe and legal abortion for the first time. The year 2007 also marked the parliamentary debate of the Human Fertilisation and Embryology Bill, which "provided the first serious parliamentary opening for anti-abortionists to drive back women's abortion rights since 1990".

The anniversary was thus an opportunity both to educate women and the public generally on the significance of the law, which had protected thousands of women from the dangers – including death – of illegal abortions, and to call for resistance to an increasingly vocal anti-abortion lobby focused on late abortions.

The 40th anniversary campaign, led by the organisation Rights for Women and

backed by many MPs, peers, doctors, nurses, sexual health organisations, trade unions and students, called for:

- abortion to be available at the request of the woman;
- an end to unacceptable delays in service provision;
- an end to attacks by the anti-choice minority on current abortion rights.

Trust funding was allocated to the organisation of a national conference focused on access to abortion for Black and other Minority Ethnic women, and refugee women survivors of violence

Women and Their Bodies Abortion Rights Mini Project (2008)

This small project, based in Israel–Palestine, involved researching chapters for a new edition of the book *Our Bodies, Ourselves*, interviewing women and collecting narratives of Palestinian and Jewish women’s experiences of abortion, and preparing information on abortion for a website in Hebrew and Arabic.

Lesbians and Feminists for the Decriminalisation of Abortion, Argentina (2010)

Following the end of the military dictatorship of 1976–1983, Argentina witnessed the flourishing of a feminist movement. Along with other Latin American and Caribbean countries (see Trinidad and Tobago, above), the Argentine women’s movement designated 28 September as “the day to celebrate the cause of abortion rights in Latin American and Caribbean countries”.

By the early twenty-first century, there was a growing campaign to overturn the section of the 1921 Penal Code that defined abortion as a crime. In 2010, the organisation *Lesbianas y Feministas por la Descriminalización del Aborto* (Lesbians and Feminists for the Decriminalisation of Abortion, LFDA) applied to the Trust for support for a programme “to prevent unsafe abortion practices at the local level by improving: access to information about safe abortion with misoprostol; access to and use of misoprostol and other resources; how to spot complications, when to seek medical care, and the legal framework protecting women’s rights in post-abortion care in hospital”. The funds would be used to “train 100 public community health workers in two municipalities, and engage with municipal government officials to make these services publicly available through the Network Against Unsafe Abortion in Argentina; the municipal health care system, and local social organizations”.

In its report to the Trust, LFDA highlighted the importance of the grant in ensuring information on abortions and availability of the morning-after pill in Argentina. On International Women’s Day (8 March) 2014 the first bill to legalise abortion up to week 14 of pregnancy was presented in the Argentine Parliament. In the subsequent years, LFDA and other organisations would contribute to the growing mass movement for abortion legalisation in the country, especially following the establishment of the *Ni Una Menos* (Not One Less) campaign to end violence against women in 2015.

Abortion Support Network (2013)

Launched in 2009, the Abortion Support Network (ASN) provided funding and support for women forced to leave Ireland to seek abortions in the UK. Established as a volunteer-run organisation and experiencing a fivefold increase in demand for their services in the first few years of their existence, ASN sought funding from the FRT to train and pay a coordinator with the aim of making their services more efficient and helping to keep the group's phone helpline open.

The Trust's funding of the ASN was an example of providing money to a difficult-to-fund project:

Abortion Support Network is the only organization giving these women practical support. ASN provides confidential and non-judgemental information, accommodation in the homes of volunteers, negotiates discounts with clinics on behalf of women and offers funding in cases of severe financial hardship. As an organization providing direct support to women in need, ASN's activities have proved hard to fund through traditional sources.

Abortion Support Network, application form to the FRT

Following the legalisation of abortion in Ireland in 2018, the Network has continued to exist, providing services "for women and pregnant people resident in Ireland, Northern Ireland, the Isle of Man, Malta, Gibraltar, Poland, Romania, Hungary, France, Spain, the Czech Republic and the other EU countries on a case-by-case basis". As of 2022–23, they were also prioritising support for those impacted by the war in Ukraine.

Calala Spain Abortion (2017)

Like Argentina, Spain's restrictions on abortion are historically the legacy of a strong Catholic Church and a military dictatorship which sought to limit women's control over their bodies and lives. Criminalised under the Franco regime, abortion was legalised in limited circumstances under democracy in the 1980s. In 2010 abortion was legalised until week 14.

In 2017, the Trust provided funding to Calala Fondo de Mujeres for a campaign "to strengthen the capacities of the feminist movement to counter anti-choice groups and discourses through networking and training activities". Calala had previously conducted research on the main anti-choice groups in Spain, discovering that these were "well organised, have a lot of resources, and copy strategies from sister organisations in the United States". As part of their research, Calala had strengthened its links to LGBTQ+ and migrants' rights groups, which were also facing increased hostility from the right.

One notable aspect of this funding is that Calala, founded in 2009, is itself a feminist funder, providing money to feminist projects in Spain and Latin America.

In early 2023, in the midst of a resurgence of the far right in the country and heated debates about gender rights, Spain's centre-left coalition government passed new legislation expanding access to abortion, meaning that 16- and 17-year-olds no longer

require their parents' consent to access abortion and abortions must be available in state hospitals. The same legislation entitles workers to paid menstrual leave and recognises the rights of transgender teenagers.

Addressing the Anti-choice Threat in Poland (2018)

Poland (another country with an historically influential Catholic Church) has some of the most restrictive abortion laws in Europe. Legalised under state socialism, abortion was prohibited by a series of laws passed after the fall of communism in 1990.

This application to the Trust came from a group of feminists who intended to study the arguments and language of right-wing anti-abortion organisations in order to counter them and promote women's right to abortion in Poland. Based in Poland, the campaign also drew on expertise from Ireland and Polish feminist groups in other parts of Europe, including the UK.

In spite of the efforts of Polish feminists and their allies elsewhere, the last abortion law, in 2021, restricted abortion to cases of assault and threat to the woman's life. However this Polish campaign, like similar ones in Argentina (2010) and Spain (2017), is an important example of feminists working to counter reactionary discourses and laws, to educate the public on the threats of anti-abortion movements and to share knowledge and resources across borders.

Abortion in Argentina (2021)

Following the legalisation of abortion up to 14 weeks in early 2021, the collective La Revuelta Feminista (Feminist Revolt) applied to the Trust for a project to provide information and facilitate access to abortion among girls and teenagers. According to their application, "Every three hours, a girl aged between 10 and 14 gives birth in Argentina. One in every six children is born to a teen mother, 69% of those pregnancies are unintended and many are the result of sexual abuse." Trust funding went to cover the cost of a telephone hotline service.

One of the last projects funded by the Trust, Feminist Revolt's initiative demonstrated that even in the context of legalisation, much feminist work remains to be done to guarantee that all those in need of abortion services can access them. Revuelta Feminista's application also provides a fitting example of how the Trust was able over the years to provide small amounts of funding to feminists in different circumstances, for projects with the potential to have an important impact on the lives of women, girls and all people seeking reproductive rights.

LESSONS

One thing we have learned is that small amounts of money do an enormous amount with feminist projects.

FR Trustee

I think the Trust should reflect on feminist tools and initiatives in a changing world, about what could have been done differently to continue to be relevant and transformative.

FR Trustee

The Feminist Review Trust was set up by small group of feminist academics, many of whom had little experience in the world of funding, but all with a fierce commitment to supporting grassroots activism. Over the years, through a system of trial and error, in addition to the accumulated experience of older Trustees and the new expertise brought by incoming members, the Trust refined its working model. More and more non-academic women joined the Trust as the auditing of Trustess highlighted the need for new kinds of skills and experience. By the time of its closure, Trustees were able to reflect on what could have been done differently and more effectively, and what lessons might be valuable for future feminist funders.

Working Model and Priorities

As noted above, the number of applications to the Trust increased astronomically over two decades. Inevitably, more and more activist work was directed to reading applications and selecting successful projects. This front-ended model of work guaranteed that all applications were considered, and careful attention went into reading and vetting them. But it also left less time for other activities, including providing more guidance to potential applicants, giving feedback on unsuccessful projects, and developing relationships with organisations whose projects had been funded.

While in the main the groups that applied for funding had strong goals and aims, with the potential to effect change in the world, many of the applications themselves were either underdeveloped or too ambitious. As noted above, this problem reflected both a lack of

resources in small feminist organisations and an inbuilt discrimination within the funding system that favoured more professional, English-speaking organisations, typically based in the global North. The Trust might have been able to promote stronger and more innovative projects if it had dedicated some of its time to providing support and advice for the kinds of small, grassroots organisations it aimed to fund. One Trustee thought that perhaps one or two Trustees could have hosted an online session every few months where groups could book time for online advice, including guidance on how to write a budget (an area in which many applicants struggled). Such a session could also have included a short presentation on what the Trust was looking for in an application, as well as a clear list of what it was *not* interested in. This kind of “low but simple helpful support”, in her words, might have strengthened the quality of applications or projects. It might also have discouraged time-consuming inappropriate, weak or “copy-cat” applications.

Fostering Feminist Ties

For many years the FRT had a dedicated Trustee to communicate and follow up with successful applications. This too was a laborious part of the process, not least because it used up the precious resources of small organisations with limited or no administrative staff. Towards the end there was a recognition that the Trust could have shifted the division of time and work away from the labour-intensive process of selecting successful applications to using more Trustees’ time to engage with funded projects and develop links with the organisations they funded. Two Trustees reflected:

If we were doing it again, we should have spent more time talking about and trying to review the impact of our money; we didn’t build that learning into the Trust.

We could have followed up proactively with everyone every few years, for example, telling them what we’d funded recently, keep those relationships alive.

One of the newer Trustees regretted in particular that Trustees did not develop closer connections with the feminists who created the most exciting and innovative programmes.

Although the Trust lacked funds to send Trustees to witness the impact of Trust funding directly, this was another area where technology could have been useful:

I wish I'd got to meet some of the people involved. Whether through Zoom, online meetings, or whatever. For them to be able to tell us about their project in person. But also for us to be able to feed back how amazing we think they are. That was a missed opportunity.

In particular, she mentioned one of the final projects funded by the Trust: an **Anti-Racist and Caring Tour** of Barcelona:

Isn't that incredible? Every year there was a project like that, where you just felt, "Oh gosh! It would be wonderful if we could take some of the funds we had and to do a trip and to see some of this on the ground." To be able to understand what it is that maybe in the next five years they would want to fund. To be a bit strategic.

Anti-Racist and Caring Tour (2022)

The Anti-Racist and Caring Tour consists of a series of tours around the city of Barcelona, provided by the activist women of *Sindihogar* (Independent Trade Union of Cleaning and Caring Workers) to generate a collective space for reflection on the colonial legacy, an historical genealogy of care work, as well as a cartography of local struggles and activist groups. It aims to produce a model of decolonial pedagogy that will be spread among pedagogical centres and platforms. Ideally, it could be used as a model by other activist collectives that could reproduce it in their own cities.

'The Tour is not simply designed to give voice to the silenced, uncomfortable stories of the city centre, but also to create alliances and strengthen our connection with local collectives. It will be supported by a series of multimedia material, such as Fanzines, Podcasts and videos. It represents a project of feminist and self-sustained economy that aims to give *Sindihogar* a long-term source of financial funding, as well as a space that values the intellectual, historical and pedagogical research that has been developed by *Sindihogar* throughout its 10 years of experience. The Feminist Review Trust grant will cover the expanses of the first phase of the project (research, training and launching).'

The above Trustee's recommendation that the Trust could have spent more time and resources strengthening its ties with some of the organisations it funded can be extended more broadly to the feminist community in which the Trust operated. Most obviously, there

could have been better communication between the Trust and the *Feminist Review* journal. While this might not have saved the Trust, dependence on *FR* contributions without more regular meetings and communication with the collective made the Trust vulnerable to the changes that were eventually made by the journal editors.

This is not to say there was no communication at all. The Chair of the Trust prepared an annual report for the Collective, which was presented to and discussed among the journal editors. In addition, there were always two members of the journal Collective on the Trust. Information flow between the two entities relied largely on the work of these two individuals, who were already busy with lots of other paid and unpaid work. While the journal and the Trust worked on an assumption of shared feminist values, and especially the ethos of collective work, these values were largely implicit. Ultimately, the relationship between the two groups could have been nurtured more carefully, on both sides.

*We relied a lot on a very informal relationship [with the Collective].
Other than the website, there was never any real documentation of what
we did and why we did it.*

FR Trustee

When the journal Collective decided to change its working model, which included halting its regular donations to the Trust, the Trust's funding model collapsed.

Financial Model

Even before the relationship between the Trust and *Feminist Review* was severed, the FRT's reliance on the collective for its annual revenue was risky: it depended upon the continuation of the financial model that had been set up at the journal. That is, it assumed that the journal would continue to turn a profit, and that the financial model of academic journals itself would not change. In other words, it was likely that sooner or later the Trust would have had to seek other sources of revenue.

Because it had such a small amount of money (about £30,000 per year), the Trust was understandably loath to spend this on anything other than funding feminist projects. But dedicating some money to hiring a professional fundraiser would have been money well spent if it had helped to guarantee the Trust's survival. As one of the original Trustees

recalls, the Trust had tried its hand at fundraising by doing a mass mail-out to feminist academics and activists based in the UK:

There was one attempt at fundraising many years ago, and we sent out a lot of letters to people we thought were our supporters and literally no one gave us any money. Because we were all embedded in socialist feminist networks we thought we didn't have to do any work about that. But actually we didn't get any money. And we were shocked. Because we expected that the work of the Trust was not only of high value to the people we were funding but also valued by other people. But apparently it wasn't.

Another Trustee noted (echoing Joan Marie Johnson's observations about the lack of women donors in the US) that more broadly there is a "lack of tradition of ensuring that people donate to feminist causes". This is a lesson that goes far beyond the Trust, pointing to an apparent paradox between the increasing professionalisation of feminism, on one hand, and the lack of a culture of donating to grassroots feminist causes, on the other.

Another dilemma related to the feminist politics of money was that, unlike large feminist foundations and NGOs, the Trust had no links to businesses. In fact, with one notable exception, Trustees did not consider themselves to be economically savvy. One of the early Trustees, now retired from her academic job, reflected with a laugh that the Trust was more like a cottage industry than a business:

It's just that we, that we're not business-minded. But also, there's something rather, how can I put it, there's something a bit over-charitable about the kind of thing that we do. We are talking about small women's organisations, very deserving. But the kind of change that's going to be brought about by that is very tiny and very incremental.

While building a nest egg might have helped to provide a buffer to sustain the Trust, in a situation of restricted funding for feminist groups that needed it in the here and now, at least one Trustee saw value in the model of spending rather than saving:

I like that we tried to spend what we got. We weren't trying to build up an endowment, which a lot of philanthropic [organisations] do.

Another Trustee wondered whether, in future, feminist funders could try models of

distributing money that would take less labour and might be more egalitarian. For every excellent project that the Trust, there were probably many other equally worthwhile ones that had to be rejected. Could we imagine a funding system, she wondered, that would involve spreading an equal amount to more organisations, to do with what they see fit (with the proviso that the project would not do actual harm)? Similarly, since many of the projects funded by the Trust aimed either to contest harmful government policies or to make up for lack of, or cuts in, state funding, especially in the UK context following the economic crisis of 2008, another Trustee asked herself whether some of the money given out by the Trust could have been better directed towards campaigning actively against austerity.

Deciding how to spend such a small amount of money involved balancing different factors in the context of a very limited budget, which inevitably meant making difficult choices. All funders face such dilemmas, and different organisations will come up with different ideas about how to allocate their resources. Perhaps other feminist funders will experiment with some of the alternative systems suggested above. Ultimately, however, as one Trustee insisted, such decisions only have meaning if there is money to spend.

The demise of the Trust highlights the high cost of the persistent underfunding of grassroots feminism.

Knowledge Preservation

Finally, the Trust's closure raised the question of how to preserve the vast knowledge and experience accumulated by individual Trustees and the Trust collectively over two decades of work. Because it prioritised the funding side of its operations, the Trust did not focus on advertising its work. This was largely a problem of resources, one that perhaps could have been improved with better collaboration with the journal. There was scope, for example, for using the expertise and networks of *Feminist Review* collective members to help successful projects link their projects with academics or to larger NGOs that could have helped to take their ideas forward. If more individuals and organisations had been directly involved in the activities of the Trust, perhaps more feminists would have had an investment in ensuring that it endured. But there was also a cultural side to this, one that grew out of the Trust's stress on solidarity rather than an ethos of self-promotion:

There wasn't the interest in shouting what we did from the rooftops, which I think came from a good place, but when the formal link with the Collective was severed there was nothing else.

Another consequence of the Trust's emphasis on praxis was a lack of time to create a systematic archive of FRT documents. Attempts were made over the years to set up a reliable, straightforward and consistent filing system of applications, minutes, decisions, communications and other matters related to the Trust, but these were uneven for a number of reasons. The lifetime of the Trust coincided with the shift from paper-based to digital systems of communication. In its early years, the Trust received hard copies of applications, and later these were sent in by email. Moreover, because the Trust never had a bricks-and-mortar headquarters, the preservation of documents related to Trust work was left to individual Trustees. Over the years, Trustees left jobs, moved offices, changed email addresses and computers. At each turn, valuable material was mislaid.

The lack of a system for gathering long-term data meant that it was difficult to draw definitive conclusions about the patterns of applications. Trustees recognised towards the end that they could have made more use of technology; but this too would have taken time, and initially, at any rate, would have taken resources away from funds for feminist projects.

This is salient reminder of the importance that *all* feminist organisations need to take care from the start to ensure that resources are dedicated to filing and archiving – both in order to ensure accountability and to leave lessons learned and a legacy for future feminist funders. One of the newer Trustees noted that the institutional memory of the Trust was largely carried in the memories of its members:

If people who had been there for a while stepped down, where would the memory go?

LBTQ Herstories in Bosnia and Herzegovina (2020)

A key source for recording the history of feminist struggle is the words of feminist activists. Over the years, the Trust funded a number of women's oral history projects, including an oral history of Rape Crisis Scotland in 2007 and Black Feminist Oral Histories in the UK in 2019.

In 2020, the Trust funded the project **Queer Archive Storytelling for Transformation: The Courageous Lives of LGBTQ Women in Bosnia and Herzegovina** (BiH). The aim of the project was “to make visible LGBTQ herstories and narratives in the LGBTQI community, the wider feminist movement and the general public of Bosnia and Herzegovina” through “recording interviews on personal accounts and herstories of LGBTQ women ... during wartime and/or the post-war period.”

The context for the project was the long-standing struggle for women’s human rights and conflict resolution among women’s civil society organisations in BiH since the period of war in the early 1990s. Even after three decades of activism on the part of women’s civil society organisations, “the majority of LGBTQ women and their stories and lives remain invisible, disconnected and undocumented ... excluded from the official narratives, completely invisible to the general public and LGBTIQ community themselves”.

The project’s aim was to record the stories of five LGBTQI women within a broader historical narrative of BiH during and after the war, including the histories of the women’s and feminist movements in the country in the late twentieth and early twenty-first centuries, and to make these narratives available and accessible to everyone online.

Following the recording of the interviews, the five oral testimonies and transcripts were published on the Queer Archive platform and promoted via social media platforms. The stories were circulated to LGBTIQ mailing lists (Spektra, Queer Montenegro, TransAid Croatia, Zagreb Pride Croatia, Zenergija Serbia, Geten Serbia, LORI Croatia) and women’s organisations across BiH, and promoted via Women’s Network, Network for Building Peace and affiliate organizations and social media, thereby contributing to the long-term goal of the Queer Archive: “to increase the visibility of LGBTIQ human rights, identities and culture through building, preserving, promoting and sharing his/herstorical records of LGBTIQ existence, arts, culture and movement in BiH”.

The oral and text interviews are accompanied by photos of the interviewees, some of whom chose to come out and others who chose to remain anonymous.

This project was one of many affected by the Covid-19 pandemic, restricting travel and forcing the interviewees to find alternative ways to record the stories (either online or in a safe in-person environment). In addition to the challenges of recording stories about war, conflict and trauma, the project participants noted that the intimate nature of telling personal stories required both finding a secure and comfortable space and building trust between the interviewer and interviewee.

Though a relatively small sample, the five interviews nevertheless allowed the participants to draw out key themes of relevance to the wider LGBTQI and women’s community in BiH:

A central topic was the perception of community, where most of [the interviewees] made parallels of the period before and during the war. Younger lesbians shared their

reflections on their hardships of coming out and their wishes for future generations.

The project also held special meaning for the interviewees themselves, one of whom shared her experience:

I think every voice should be heard, especially voices of minority groups who have no rights in the 21st century. We as women live in patriarchal society and our voices are often very quiet. Being a lesbian or bisexual woman is very hard in the Balkans. We should raise our voices, inspire each other and support younger generations, older generations as well. We need to have each other's back and support each other. I think personal stories are important and we need to push them in the public space. It might raise awareness and some young lesbians or queer women might be encouraged ... to take their life into their own hands and live it fully!

The oral history project led the members of the Kvir arhiv (Queer Archive) to undertake new projects in women's and lesbian history. As of September 2022, they were planning a documentary movie about Lepa Mladjenovic, a pioneer of lesbian, anti-war and feminist activism.²⁴

LGBTQ Herstories is a reminder that feminist activism is about more than direct intervention in women's everyday lives, campaigning for changes to policy, or providing key structural changes to challenge gender and other hierarchies. It is also about bearing witness, recording the stories of women's lives and struggles. Through funding this and other oral history projects over the years, the Trust also contributed to the preservation and dissemination of this crucial feminist history.

²⁴ The LGBTQ Herstories interviews and transcripts are available at <http://www.kvirarhiv.org/archives/684> (Bosnian) and <http://www.kvirarhiv.org/en/archives/693> (English)

LEGACIES

The Trust funded a lot of risky things, compared to a lot of funders – a lot of our grants weren't huge successes, but we funded a lot of precarious organisations, people who hadn't been funded before; we didn't require groups to be registered or have a long history; we tended to say that those groups who had histories of funding didn't need our money; we funded things that weren't necessarily going to lead to bigger projects.

FR Trustee

New types of activism and funding are emerging – movements and protests, global online collaborations facilitated by social media, crowdfunding for projects, and the rise of new bigger feminist funds that in theory and principle are committed to grassroots funding. However, it is not yet clear that in practice this is the case. With greater professionalisation, overheads, systems of tracking and learning, it may indeed be small community-inspired initiatives of the kind the FRT funded, that will lose out – not all are media friendly, or high profile, or identified with individual changemakers.

Eleanor O'Gorman, author of "Funding Feminist Change"

I'm proud that we've given away half a million quid over twenty years. Probably none of it's been wasted, it's all done some good to some women somewhere. I'm proud that we set up the Trust because it was a unique and very feminist project. I don't know of anything that's anything like it. So I think it's unique and very special and I'm very proud to have been part of that, which is why I want these histories done. I don't want it forgotten.

FR Trustee

In 1938, Virginia Woolf famously argued that if women wanted to change the world and prevent war, they needed not only education and access to professions: they needed money. Woolf would no doubt have been amazed at the flourishing of the transnational feminist movement that emerged in the decades after her lifetime; but she would still have grave cause for concern about the dearth of funding for women's causes in comparison with male-dominated political movements (and indeed, their sports, entertainment and leisure

pursuits). Almost one hundred years after the publication of *Three Guineas*, the question of who fund women's – and specifically *feminists* – projects remain urgent, not least in the context of a global shift to the right, a growing anti-feminist backlash and the unrelenting challenges posed by neoliberal hegemony.

At an institutional level, the response to these challenges, whether within academia or within the funding sector, has often been to champion big, showy projects, ones that can easily showcase feminism's public "impact". As a feminist project that grew out of an activist academic journal, the Feminist Review Trust followed a different path, inspired by the belief that small amounts of money can make a substantial difference, that women working together voluntarily can resist some of the most destructive impacts of capitalism and patriarchy, and that "impacts" can be measured not only in metrics but in the less perceptible ways that feminist projects change the lives of women, individually and as a group.

While much work went into learning about how the Trust's money had made a difference to the women it funded, and to tracking the progress (and in some cases the demise) of specific projects, what is more difficult to quantify and capture is the impact of feminist funding on the people who created and ran the projects themselves, many of whom went on to do other feminist work. This is what one Trustee referred to as the "snowball effect" of feminist funding and activism:

I think the job we were doing was very important and in small-scale ways positively affected the lives of women in different places. Absolutely. We've never done an ethnographic study of the organisations we supported and what they were doing in their localities in terms of links with other organisations. But it does add up.

In the process of researching this history of the Feminist Review Trust, I looked up some of the women who had applied for and received Trust funding over the years. Although several of the organisations that they had worked or volunteered for had subsequently shut down, and many of the individual applicants had moved on to other positions, a number continued to do different kinds of feminist activism: in the charity and NGO sectors, as researchers, as freelance journalists or filmmakers, writers or artists. It is impossible to

measure in quantitative terms the long-term impact of the work they did with the small amounts of money they received from the Trust. But those I communicated with emphasised that they carried this experience with them in the work they have continued to do, and that they also helped to change ideas and attitudes among people around them.

As one of the young women journalists in Peru who hosted the radio programme Chicha Morada (see above) wrote:

Feminism gives us the tools that we can use to start to change the mindset of our audience, mostly young people between 18 and 35, opening the doors for them to question discrimination by talking about issues that are rarely discussed in mainstream media. [Trust] financing allowed us to develop new creative ways for educating, questioning and transforming people when confronting something that affects us all: sexism.

It is in this day-to-day work of feminist change – often ephemeral, always ongoing – that the Feminist Review Trust lives on.

Carrie Lou Hamilton

Carrie Lou Hamilton is a freelance editor, researcher, translator and writer based in London. She was a member of the *Feminist Review* editorial collective between 2011 and 2019, and a Feminist Review Trustee from 2013 to 2018. Her latest book is *Veganism, Sex and Politics: Tales of Danger and Pleasure* (2019); she publishes a regular newsletter on writing and activism: <https://peninfist.substack.com>. For more about her writing and other projects, see <https://linktr.ee/clouhamilton>.

